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Final Master Thesis

Project Management of a Self-sustainable House
in Sant Vicenç dels Horts

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INDEX

1. INTRODUCTION.....	9
2. CONTEXT	10
2.1 The Operational Environment.....	10
2.1.1 Political Analysis	10
2.1.2 Economic Analysis	10
2.1.3 Social Analysis	12
2.1.4 Technological Analysis	12
2.1.5 Legal Analysis	13
2.1.6 Environmental Analysis.....	13
2.2 Sector Analysis.....	14
2.2.1 Sector Introduction	14
2.2.2 Business Model.....	16
2.3 Company Introduction.....	17
2.3.1 Generic.....	17
2.3.2 Strategic	17
2.3.3 Operative.....	22
2.3.4 Project Management	23
2.4 Fitting	25
2.4.1 Viability	25
2.4.2 Alignment with Business Objectives.....	26
2.4.3 Impact at Organizational Level	27
2.4.4 Regulations	28
3. Definition of the Project.....	31
3.1 General Description of the Project	31
3.2 SWOT/PREN Analysis	33
3.3 Critical Success Factors (CSFs)	34
3.4 Alternative Scenario	35
3.5 Stakeholder Analysis	38
4. Project Charter	41
5. Planning of the Project.....	50
5.1 Stakeholder Plan.....	50
5.1.1 Stakeholder analysis	50
5.1.2 Action Plan	55
5.2 Communications Management Plan.....	58
5.2.1 Communication Strategy	58
5.2.2 Stakeholder Communication Requirements	59
5.2.3 Communication Channels.....	68
5.2.4 Communication Control and Monitoring	70
5.2.5 Communication Standards.....	73
5.2.6 Communication Flowchart	73
5.2.7 Guidelines for Meetings	74
5.3 Scope Definition	77
5.3.1 Requirements	77
5.3.2 Project Scope	79

5.3.3	Product Scope	80
5.3.4	Work Breakdown Structure (WBS).....	82
5.3.5	WBS Dictionary.....	83
5.4	Procurement Management Plan.....	85
5.4.1	Procurement Strategy.....	86
5.4.2	Identification and Categorization	86
5.4.3	Purchase Documents.....	88
5.5	Quality Management Plan	89
5.6	Schedule Management Plan	101
5.6.1	Timeline	101
5.6.2	Critical Path	106
5.6.3	Milestone Plan	108
5.7.	Transition and Handover	109
5.7.1	Project Life Cycle	110
5.7.2	Milestone and Deliverables	111
5.7.3	Project Transition.....	112
5.7.4	Transition Team and Responsibility	113
5.7.5	Property Transition	115
5.7.6	Knowledge Transfer	116
5.7.7	Project Transition Schedule.....	117
5.7.8	Handover and Acceptance Criteria.....	117
5.8.	Resource Management Plan	119
5.8.1	Resource breakdown structure (RBS)	120
5.8.2	Organization Structure of the project (OBS)	121
5.8.3	Roles	122
5.8.4	Responsibilities Matrix (RACI).....	126
5.8.5	Resource Utilization Plan	127
5.9	Risk Management Plan.....	128
5.9.1	Description of the Risk	129
5.9.2	Qualitative Risk Analysis	130
5.9.3	Response Plan.....	132
5.9.3	Quantitative Risk Analysis	133
5.9.4	Risk Sheet	134
5.10	Cost Management Plan.....	135
5.10.1	Project Budget	135
5.10.2	Cost Analysis	135
5.10.3	Treasury and Financing Plan	137
6.	Project Control.....	138
6.1	The Change Control System.....	138
6.1.1	Change Control Flow.....	138
6.1.2	Change Control Committee	140
6.1.3	Change Control Sheet.....	142
6.2	Change Management Case	142
7.	Closure	146
7.1	Criteria for Validation and Acceptance of Results.....	146
7.2	Closure of Suppliers	150
7.2.1	Supplier Evaluation	152
7.2.2	Contract Closure	153

7.3 Satisfactory Survey.....	154
7.4 Administrative Closure.....	160
7.4.1 Financial Closure	160
7.4.2 Management of Documentation	162
7.4.3 Steps for Handover	162
7.5 Service Level Agreements	164
7.5.1 Project Penalties.....	165
7.5.2 Project Guarantees	166
8. Conclusions	167
9. Recommendation for its Practical Application	168
9.1 Future Study Lines.....	169
BIBLIOGRAPHY & WEBLIOGRAPHY	170

CONTENT LIST

Illustration 1: Comparison of Subsidies (own creation)	11
Illustration 2: Social Analysis/Factor Influencing Project Success (own creation)	12
Illustration 3: Business Model Canvas (own creation)	16
Illustration 4: Operating cash flow.....	21
Illustration 5: Bar graphics of financial data	22
Illustration 6: Organization Structure of the Company.....	23
Illustration 7: Waterfall Mode Specific for the Project.....	24
Illustration 8: SWOT Analysis (own creation)	33
Illustration 9: PREN Analysis (own creation)	33
Illustration 10: Power/Interest Matrix	40
Illustration 11: Salience Model	40
Illustration 12: P/I Matrix.....	54
Illustration 13: Project Communication Flowchart.....	73
Illustration 14: Work Breakdown Structure (WBS).....	82
Illustration 15: MS Project Timeline.....	105
Illustration 16: MS Project Critical Path	106
Illustration 17: Project Life Cycle.....	110
Illustration 18: Resource Breakdown Structure (RBS).....	120
Illustration 19: Organization Structure of the project (OBS).....	121
Illustration 20: Responsibilities Matrix (RACI)	126
Illustration 21: Resource Utilization Plan Chart	127
Illustration 22: Risk Breakdown Structure (RBS)	129
Illustration 23: Impact and Probability Criteria	130
Illustration 24: Materials Cost Distribution Pie Chart	137
Illustration 25: Monthly Money Tracker "S" Curve	137
Illustration 26: Change Control Structure	140
Illustration 27: Financial Closure Diagram.....	161
Illustration 28: Steps for Managing Documentation	164

TABLE LIST

Table 1: Generic information of the company	17
Table 2: Projected Financial Ratios	21
Table 3: General Description of the Project.....	32
Table 4: Critical Success Factors (CSF's)	35
Table 5: Alternative Scenarios Analysis	35
Table 6: Alternative Scenario 1.....	36
Table 7: Alternative Scenario 2.....	36
Table 8: Alternative Scenario 3.....	37
Table 9: Internal Stakeholder Analysis	38
Table 10: External Stakeholder Analysis	39
Table 11: P/I Matrix	39
Table 12: Project Charter (own creation).....	49
Table 13: Stakeholder Analysis.....	53
Table 14: Updated P/I Matrix.....	54
Table 15: Action Plan.....	57
Table 16: Project’s Communication Roles and Responsibilities	68
Table 17: The Project Communication Channels	68
Table 18: Project Communication Control and Monitoring	72
Table 19: Project Communication Matrix.....	75
Table 20: Project Stakeholder Register (internal)	76
Table 21: Project Stakeholder Register (external)	76
Table 22: Scope Requirements	79
Table 23: Project Scope.....	80
Table 24: Product Scope	81
Table 25: WBS Dictionary	85
Table 26: Procurement Strategy	86
Table 27: Identification and Category of Procurement Strategy.....	87
Table 28: Cost Distribution Pie Chart	87
Table 29: Purchase Package Documents.....	89
Table 30: Product Objectives for Continuous Improvement.....	92
Table 31: Project Objectives for Continuous Improvement.....	93
Table 32: Quality Control for Implementation of Architectural and Engineering Designs.....	93
Table 33: Quality Control for Construction Waste Reduction.....	93
Table 34: Quality control for Rainwater Collection.....	94
Table 35: Quality control for Installation of Solar Panels	94
Table 36: Quality Control for Delivering All Project Deliverables on Time.....	95
Table 37: Quality Assurance Metrics for Product.....	96
Table 38: Quality Assurance Metrics for Project.....	97
Table 39: Key Quality Roles and Responsibilities.....	100
Table 40: Critical Path.....	107
Table 41: Milestone Plan.....	108
Table 42: Project Life Cycle and Deliverable Acceptance	112
Table 43: Transition Activities and Documents Required	113
Table 44: Transition Committee Roles and Responsibilities	114
Table 45: Training Sessions Schedule	116
Table 46: Project Transition Schedule	117
Table 47: Project Handover Information	118
Table 48: Resources Roles	124
Table 49: Sustainability Architect Role Analysis	125
Table 50: Qualitative Risk Analysis.....	131
Table 51: Response Plan	133
Table 52: Quantitative Risk Analysis.....	134

Table 53: Risk Sheet	134
Table 54: Human Resources Cost Analysis	136
Table 55: Material Resources Cost Analysis	136
Table 56: Change Control Committee Members	141
Table 57: Change Control Board - Decision Sheet	141
Table 58: Change Control Sheet	142
Table 59: Change Management Case.....	144
Table 60: Change Control Sheet.....	144
Table 61: Change Control Board - Decision Request.....	145
Table 62: Change Request Number	145
Table 63: Project Acceptance Criteria.....	148
Table 64: Scope Validation	149
Table 65: Lessons Learned.....	149
Table 66: Financial Indicators.....	150
Table 67: Content Final Supplier Closure Report.....	152
Table 68: Suppliers Evaluation Metrics	153
Table 69: Stages of Contract Closure.....	154
Table 70: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for project team members	156
Table 71: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for stakeholders (internal)	157
Table 72: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for client	157
Table 73: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for local council	158
Table 74: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for suppliers.....	159
Table 75: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for community members	160
Table 76: Project Penalties	166

1. INTRODUCTION

In the face of growing environmental concerns and the drive for sustainable development, Self-sustainable House emerges as innovative and revolutionary solutions in the building and construction industry. This project is about the project management for designing and executing a self-sustainable building in Sant Vicenç dels Horts, Catalonia, Spain.

Self-sustainable House are designed to operate independently of traditional municipal utilities, using renewable energy sources and efficient water and waste management systems. These buildings reduce their environmental impact by harnessing clean energy, recycling water, sourcing materials locally, and incorporating green technologies like living walls and green roofs. Their comprehensive approach to sustainability not only minimizes reliance on external resources but also enhances resident well-being. The project management plan for implementing this building aims to address global environmental challenges, contributing to climate action and sustainable development through innovative and responsible practices.

EcoBuild Solutions is a renowned construction company that prides itself as a leading environmentally friendly property developer in Europe. The company's strategic mission is the clarity of paths to creating and delivering sustainable high-quality construction solutions. Our vision anchors on active participation and leading the change in the ever-evolving construction industry while maintaining integrity and quality products. At EcoBuild Solutions, our products and services are built on core values including but not limited to versatility, innovation, client-focus and sustainability.

The project scope involves the management of all the phases of the project cycle including initiation, planning, execution, monitoring and closure scheduled for completion within 12 months. The product scope includes designing and constructing a house that incorporates facilities for self-energy generation, water supply, sustainable building materials and environmental sustainability. The schedule will be presented in a Gantt chart highlighting the project work packages, milestones, critical paths and slacks at each stage. The total project cost is estimated at 500,000 euros.

The project management approach adopts a stepwise traditional predictive strategy involving pre-planning, design and execution using a waterfall method. This project will be managed and executed using resources that will be acquired both internally and externally.

2. CONTEXT

2.1 The Operational Environment

The following PESTLE analysis evaluates the factors that will influence the correct management of the project plan to develop a residential building that self-sustains itself with minimal dependence on municipal utilities in the town of Sant Vincenç dels Horts. Project managed by *EcoBuild Solutions*, a company specialized in sustainable construction and renewable energy systems.

2.1.1 Political Analysis

The government support for sustainability in Spain, particularly Catalonia, has a strong alignment with the European Union's climate and energy policies that actively promote sustainable development.

The Spanish government offers various incentives, grants, and subsidies for green projects, that represents a leverage to finance key components of the project. Additionally, consider that Sant Vicenç dels Horts is subject to Catalonia's building and environmental regulations, which are relatively strict regarding energy efficiency, renewable energy use, and water management, reason why we must ensure compliance with these standards because a key aspect of our project management will involve liaising with local authorities to navigate zoning laws, permitting, and environmental impact assessments.

2.1.2 Economic Analysis

From an economic perspective, our project budget of €500,000 and 12-month timeline needs meticulous financial management to avoid cost overruns. Material and labor costs in Catalonia, along with potential inflation-driven price fluctuations, require close monitoring. Prioritizing locally sourced building materials helps reduce import taxes and transportation costs.

To enhance financial feasibility, we'll explore Spain's incentives for green construction, the long-term financial benefits include reduced utility costs due to self-sufficiency, making the project more attractive overall. Some of these incentives and subsidies available that could support the development of the project, are:

1. **NextGenerationEU Funds:** Provides significant financial support for energy-efficient projects. The funds are available for home renovations aimed at improving energy efficiency by at least 30%, with subsidies ranging from 40% to 80% of the project costs depending on the level of energy reduction achieved.
2. **Local Incentives for Solar Energy:** Catalonia offers municipal-level tax reductions such as discounts on the ICIO (Tax on Constructions, Installations, and Works) and the IBI (Property Tax). Depending on the municipality, these reductions can cover up to 95% of the ICIO tax for solar installations.

The following bar chart illustrates the potential subsidy percentages available between the **NextGenerationEU** and **Local Solar Energy Incentives** in Catalonia. It highlights the minimum and maximum subsidy or tax reduction percentages available:

Illustration 1: Comparison of Subsidies (own creation)

These programs, combined with other regional and national support, could significantly reduce the financial burden of incorporating renewable energy systems into the project.

2.1.3 Social Analysis

Community involvement and acceptance are paramount for the project. Sant Vicenç dels Horts is a town full of urban and rural elements that may present diverse levels of support for self-sustainable buildings. EcoBuild Solutions will engage with local stakeholders through consultations and educational programs to raise awareness about sustainable construction and foster community buy-in that will help to mitigate opposition and generate local interest.

The strong regional identity and progressive attitudes toward sustainability create a favorable environment for the project’s integration into the community, as the region increasingly embraces environmental protection as a core value.

Illustration 2: Social Analysis/Factor Influencing Project Success (own creation)

Note The percentages in the pie chart above are illustrative estimates and not based on any specific data. We distributed the values equally with a slight emphasis on **Community Engagement** (40%) as it’s likely a more significant factor in the social analysis, considering the need for public acceptance and participation.

2.1.4 Technological Analysis

Advanced Technologies in Sustainable Construction: The projects will rely on the integration of sustainable technologies, such as: solar panels, wind turbines, water recycling systems, and composting. These technologies will further reduce the building’s environmental impact and operational costs.

Access to Skilled Labor and Expertise: The construction of the self-sustainable house requires specialized labor and expertise in green construction and renewable energy systems.

EcoBuild Solutions will source skilled workers locally and tap into the talent pool available nearby Barcelona. The company will also rely on external consultants for specific areas.

Integration of Smart Home Technology: In addition to sustainable technologies, automation systems will be integrated to monitor and optimize energy and water usage. These systems will enhance the building's efficiency, allowing residents to control and reduce consumption in real time.

2.1.5 Legal Analysis

Compliance with Environmental Laws: Spain and the EU have rigorous environmental regulations that will impact the construction and operation of the self-sustainable building. Key areas of compliance include energy efficiency, water use, waste disposal, and environmental impact assessments. EcoBuild Solutions will need to ensure that the project complies with these regulations to avoid legal issues or delays in obtaining permits. Collaborating with legal advisors who specialize in environmental law will be critical to the smooth execution of the project.

Contractual Obligations and Supplier Agreements: EcoBuild Solutions will also need to manage its relationships with suppliers and subcontractors through clear contracts to ensure the timely delivery of materials and services.

The company must secure contracts for the supply of renewable energy systems, construction materials, and skilled labor while ensuring all parties comply with local labor laws and safety standards.

2.1.6 Environmental Analysis

Mediterranean Climate Considerations: The Mediterranean climate in Sant Vicenç dels Horts, characterized by hot, dry summers and mild winters, is conducive to the installation of solar energy systems, which will be a core component of the building's self-sufficiency. However, the project will also need to account for water conservation strategies, as the region can experience droughts. Efficient water recycling systems and rainwater harvesting technologies will mitigate the risk of water scarcity affecting the building's operation.

Sustainability and Environmental Impact: The entire project is centered on minimizing its ecological footprint. By sourcing building materials locally, using green roofs and incorporating renewable energy and water management systems, EcoBuild Solutions aims to create a prototype for future sustainable developments. Waste management will be handled using on-site composting and recycling systems, further reducing the building's reliance on municipal infrastructure and contributing to the overall sustainability goals.

2.2 Sector Analysis

2.2.1 Sector Introduction

The self-sustainable building sector in Spain is gaining momentum as the country shifts towards greener, more sustainable construction practices. This sector operates at the intersection of the construction, renewable energy, and environmental sustainability industries. Its focus is on designing, constructing, and managing buildings that significantly reduce reliance on traditional municipal infrastructure by incorporating renewable energy sources, water recycling systems, and efficient waste management technologies. The rise of this sector is largely driven by Spain's commitment to lowering carbon emissions, improving energy efficiency, and promoting sustainable development.

EcoBuild Solutions, the company overseeing this project, is part of this growing sector, responding to the increasing demand for environmentally friendly housing in Spain. The demand is driven by both regulatory pressures and consumer preferences for homes that are not only energy-efficient but also environmentally conscious. Recent studies suggest that nearly 70% of new homeowners in Spain now consider energy efficiency a top priority when choosing a home, making sustainable construction a key factor in the future of the real estate market.

Key factors shaping this sector in Spain include:

- ◆ **Technological Advancements in Energy Systems:** The development of renewable energy technologies, such as solar panels and wind turbines. Innovations in energy storage, smart grids, and energy management systems are enabling buildings to become more self-sufficient.
- ◆ **Government Regulations:** Spain has set ambitious targets to reduce carbon emissions and promote renewable energy use with some building regulations such as: Código

Técnico de la Edificación (or CTE) that include stringent energy efficiency requirements for new constructions, renewable energy use, and waste management. These regulations align with broader environmental policies, as its the National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC), which aims to transition towards a low-carbon economy.

- ◆ **Financial Incentives for Green Projects:** The Spanish government provide various financial incentives to encourage sustainable construction. That includes tax breaks, grants, and low-interest loans for projects that incorporate renewable energy and energy efficiency measures. Additionally, programs like the “*Next Generation EU*” funds also provide financial resources for green initiatives, which can be leveraged for self-sustainable building projects.
- ◆ **Public Acceptance and Demand:** There is growing public awareness and support for environmentally sustainable buildings in Spain, particularly among younger generations. Homebuyers are increasingly prioritizing energy efficiency and sustainability, not just for environmental reasons but also for long-term cost savings. According to a survey by the Spanish Green Building Council, nearly 80% of respondents believe that sustainable homes will become the norm within the next decade. This shift in consumer behavior is influencing both the residential and commercial real estate markets, pushing developers to integrate sustainability into their projects.
- ◆ **Local Focus on Sustainability:** In Catalonia, where this project is located, there is a government support for sustainability initiatives such as the “*Pla Estratègic Metropolità de Barcelona*” (PEMB) focus on promoting sustainable urban development and integrating green energy solutions into city planning.

2.2.2 Business Model

The Business Model Canvas presented below provides a structured overview of the strategic components essential for the successful implementation of the self-sustainable housing project.

This model outlines key aspects such as value propositions, customer segments, key activities, and revenue streams. By addressing these components, EcoBuild Solutions ensures a balanced and comprehensive approach to meeting market demands while achieving sustainability goals. The canvas also highlights partnerships, resources, and cost structures, which are pivotal for operational efficiency and financial feasibility.

Illustration 3: Business Model Canvas (own creation)

2.3 Company Introduction

2.3.1 Generic

EcoBuild Solutions is a growing family company with 9 years of experience in construction. We like to innovate with materials and systems and give great quality to our products and services. We make both the design and execution of houses and buildings.

Name	EcoBuild Solutions
Type of company	Family Company
Legal Form	Private Limited Liability Company
Registration Date	2015
Registration Capital	500.500,00 €
Address	Av/ de Roma 76, Barcelona
Business Scope	Design and construction of houses Design and construction of buildings

Table 1: Generic information of the company

2.3.2 Strategic

To accomplish the success of the project, we need to have and follow a clear and determined strategy.

Mission

Our mission is to deliver high-quality construction solutions across a wide range of projects, from residential homes to commercial buildings, with a commitment to excellence, innovation, and client satisfaction. As a family-owned company, we build not just structures but trust and long-lasting relationships with our clients, ensuring that each project meets the highest standards of quality and safety.

Vision

We aim to be recognized as a leading construction company that adapts to the evolving needs of the industry and our clients, while remaining rooted in our family values of integrity, quality, and service. We aim to expand our capabilities across residential, commercial, and sustainable construction, becoming a trusted name for projects of all sizes.

Core Values

We promote many core values:

◆ **Versatility**

We pride ourselves on our ability to take on a wide variety of construction projects, from traditional residential homes to complex commercial developments. Our team is equipped with the skills and expertise to adapt to different client needs, ensuring that every project is completed to the highest standard, no matter the scope.

◆ **Innovation and Sustainability**

While we are experienced in traditional construction, we are also committed to staying ahead of industry trends by adopting new technologies and sustainable building practices. Our recent venture into self-sustainable housing reflects our dedication to innovation. We strive to integrate eco-friendly solutions, such as renewable energy systems and sustainable materials, into suitable projects, ensuring a better future for both our clients and the environment.

◆ **Quality Craftsmanship**

Every project we undertake is built with care and attention to detail. Whether it's a large commercial building or a small family home, our team is committed to delivering exceptional craftsmanship that ensures durability, safety, and aesthetic appeal. Quality is the foundation upon which we build, and it is what sets us apart in the industry.

◆ **Client-Focused Approach**

Our clients are at the heart of everything we do. We believe in clear, transparent communication throughout the construction process and work closely with clients to ensure their needs and expectations are met. Whether they seek a modern commercial

space or an environmentally sustainable home, we tailor our approach to meet their specific goals, ensuring a smooth and rewarding experience.

◆ **Family and Integrity**

As a family-owned business, we operate with the values of trust, honesty, and respect. Our relationships with our clients, employees, and partners are built on these principles, ensuring that we foster long-term connections based on mutual respect and shared success. We approach every project with the same level of care and integrity that has earned us the trust of our community.

◆ **Community Impact**

We are committed to giving back to the communities we build in. Whether through the creation of sustainable housing or traditional developments, we aim to enhance the well-being and quality of life in the areas we serve. Our focus on community development extends beyond construction, with initiatives aimed at supporting local economies and fostering environmental responsibility.

Tagline:

"Building Today, Sustaining Tomorrow"

This tagline reflects our commitment to high-quality construction across many projects, while emphasizing the forward-thinking, sustainable practices that define our recent focus on self-sustainable housing.

Company's Objectives:

Medium-Term Objectives (Next 2-5 Years)

- ◆ Deliver high-quality construction across diverse projects, ensuring safety, and durability.
- ◆ Expand sustainable construction initiatives by integrating eco-friendly designs, renewable energy systems, and sustainable materials into more projects.
- ◆ Meet and exceed client expectations of our clients by maintaining clear communication, delivering on time and within budget, and tailoring solutions to client needs.

- ◆ Foster innovation in construction practices by investing in new technologies to improve efficiency and sustainability.
- ◆ Build long-lasting relationships with clients, partners, and stakeholders, emphasizing integrity and trust.

Long-Term Objectives (Beyond 5 Years)

- ◆ Become a leader in construction across Spain and Europe, setting new standards for building practices.
- ◆ Reduce the environmental impact of all projects by using sustainable materials, minimizing waste, and aligning new buildings with green certifications.
- ◆ Support community growth and development by creating spaces that foster long-term social and economic growth while improving quality of life.
- ◆ Maintain strong financial health for long-term growth, pursuing profitable traditional and sustainable projects to ensure the company's stability.
- ◆ Expand the reach of self-sustainable housing, making it more affordable and accessible to a broader market through innovative design and cost-effective construction.
- ◆ Innovate continuously in building techniques and technologies, ensuring that the company remains at the forefront of sustainable and efficient construction methods.

Sources and Uses of Funds

As an experienced family-run business, we are well-equipped to manage the financial aspects of the project. The required capital for the project has been carefully allocated from our resources to cover both the design and construction phases.

A detailed financial plan will be provided later, building on our solid track record and sound financial statements, which demonstrate our ability to successfully execute this project.

The financial data for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023 has been prepared to demonstrate that the company has financial health and is a growing company. The data includes key figures like Revenue, Operating Costs, Gross Profit, Net Income, and Cash Reserves.

Free Cash Flow Statement

Another crucial financial report is the cash flow statement, which is essential for tracking the inflows and outflows of money. This report is vital for managing purchases, investments, and revenue generated from sales. In our company's financial documentation, we have estimated a free cash flow for this year and the next one and compared them to previous years. The free cash flow is particularly important as it will be used to calculate key financial metrics such as IRR (Internal Rate of Return), ROI (Return on Investment), ROA (Return on Assets), GPM (Gross Profit Margin), and NPM (Net Profit Margin). The free cash flow statement is shown in the following graph:

Illustration 4: Operating cash flow

Payback Period

The payback period is reporting an approximate calculation of how long the capital all the way back to set up a business.

Internal Ratio Analysis

A financial analysis has been made to evaluate the ratios like ROA, ROE, ROI, GPM and NPM. We used the real data for the past years and estimated for 2025. This is shown in Table X.

METRIC	2023	2024	2025
ROA	16.23%	30.17%	72.95%
ROE	21.64%	40.23%	97.26%
Gross Profit Margin	26.91%	21.74%	27.30%
Net Profit Margin	9.64%	9.26%	14.37%
ROI	13.39%	13.89%	20.12%

Table 2: Projected Financial Ratios

Illustration 5: Bar graphics of financial data

2.3.3 Operative

EcoBuild solutions is a construction family company with great experience in both the design and the execution of houses and buildings. Our years of experience with construction and our interest in innovation and sustainability gives our products and projects the quality and standards we are known for and we are proud of being recognized for it.

The success of a construction company relies heavily on a strong foundation of organization and management. An efficient, well-coordinated management team is crucial to ensuring that each of the projects of the company runs smoothly, from design to construction.

Our company has now 45 employees, allowing us to have a level of precision and teamwork is essential for delivering high-quality projects that meet the goals of sustainability and innovation.

We have a Finance department, Construction department, Procurements department, Quality control department, health and safety department and a marketing department. This is shown in the next chart:

Illustration 6: Organization Structure of the Company

2.3.4 Project Management

Our company has a project manager in charge of each of the projects, we don't have a PMO office, but we have experienced and efficient project managers who achieve the goals and objectives in the projects they manage. Throughout our years of experience, we have formed a team of committed and trained people.

Each project is carefully planned, from the time, resources, risks, budget, and communication, to the control phase in the execution are taken care of by the assigned project manager and informed to the stakeholders defined for each of the projects. Each project manager defines, for his/her project, the methodology of management considered the most adequate in each case. We hold a monthly meeting to review all the projects in course in the company.

For the construction of a self-sustainable house, the project management mode and structure are critical to its success. In this case, as there isn't a project management office, the project manager is responsible of making sure the project follows a structured and sequential approach, starting with detailed design and planning, followed by procurement of sustainable materials, and then the construction phase, as shown in the plan. The team will be optimized for each stage, with specialists like environmental engineers and sustainable architects playing key roles in the early stages. As the project progresses, additional on-site construction staff and supervisors will join to ensure the building is executed flawlessly, with a focus on eco-friendly practices.

The operational plan for this project outlines how each phase will be executed to meet the objectives of sustainability, energy efficiency, and environmental responsibility. In this context,

self-sustainable house construction requires stringent processes to ensure high-quality materials are sourced, waste is minimized, and renewable energy systems are integrated into the design. Operational procedures will also include regular inspections and quality checks to maintain high standards throughout the building.

To manage this project efficiently, we consider the waterfall project management methodology is the most suitable approach. This method is ideal for construction projects like this, as it provides a linear and well-defined structure. Each phase; planning, design, material procurement, and construction, is completed before moving to the next, reducing the risk of costly changes or rework later in the project. By using the waterfall method, we ensure that sustainability goals are thoroughly incorporated in the planning and design phases, and every step can be meticulously reviewed to meet these high standards before moving forward.

Illustration 7: Waterfall Mode Specific for the Project

2.4 Fitting

2.4.1 Viability

The self-sustainable housing market is growing, especially in regions where environmental awareness and energy efficiency are increasingly valued. Compared to other housing developments, this project offers several key advantages:

- ◆ **Cost-Effectiveness:**

Unlike conventional housing projects that rely on external energy and water supplies, this self-sustainable house integrates renewable energy systems, such as solar panels and water recycling systems, which significantly reduce long-term operational costs. By reducing reliance on public utilities, homeowners can save up to 50% on monthly energy consumption compared to traditional homes, offering a highly cost-effective alternative. Furthermore, by using at least 70% of sustainable and recycled materials, the project aligns with global sustainability trends, making it both eco-friendly and financially viable in the long term.

- ◆ **Investment Return and Payback Period:**

Based on previous construction projects and market analysis, we project that the total investment for this project will remain within the **€500,000** budget. Given the efficiency of the construction timeline (12 months) and the significant cost savings on energy, the payback period for this self-sustainable house is expected to be shorter compared to conventional housing developments. Homeowners can recover their costs through energy savings within a projected period of **3 to 4 years**, thanks to reduced utility expenses and the potential for surplus energy generation, which can be sold back to the grid.

- ◆ **Impact of Innovative Systems:**

The advanced energy and water management systems integrated into this self-sustainable house are designed to be monitored and optimized via a smart home system. This monitoring capability ensures that the systems operate at peak efficiency, leading to even greater long-term savings. Additionally, the ability to monitor and control all systems from a central hub gives homeowners full control of their energy and water

consumption, promoting a new standard of living that is both sustainable and cost-effective.

2.4.2 Alignment with Business Objectives

The self-sustainable house project is an excellent reflection of our company's objectives. It allows us to expand into sustainable construction while continuing to meet high standards of quality, client satisfaction, and innovation. The project also strengthens our financial health, supports community growth, invests in employee development, and contributes to the reduction of environmental impact, aligning with our long-term vision and values.

In the medium-term, the project demonstrates the company's ability to deliver high-quality construction while embracing sustainability. It serves as a key example of the company's growing focus on integrating renewable energy systems, energy-efficient designs, and recycled materials into its construction portfolio. The self-sustainable house is also central to the company's aim to develop and promote self-sustainable housing as a core offering, positioning the company as a forward-thinking player in the market. Furthermore, this project fosters innovation in construction practices, giving the team hands-on experience with cutting-edge technologies and eco-friendly solutions. It also strengthens client relationships by meeting the increasing demand for eco-friendly living solutions and demonstrates the company's dedication to client satisfaction.

In the long-term, this project serves as a foundation for achieving leadership in the sustainable construction sector. By reducing the environmental impact of the construction process and producing a home that operates independently of public utilities, the project supports the goal of becoming a leader in eco-friendly construction. Additionally, the self-sustainable house is a model for community growth, as it encourages the development of energy-efficient and environmentally responsible housing solutions. The experience gained through this project will contribute to the company's continuous innovation in building techniques, ensuring that future projects are aligned with both green certifications and evolving industry technologies.

Overall, the self-sustainable house project is a pivotal step in meeting the company's medium-term goals of growth, innovation, and sustainability while setting the stage for achieving its long-term vision of becoming a leader in the sustainable construction industry.

2.4.3 Impact at Organizational Level

The successful implementation of this self-sustainable house project will have several key impacts on the organization:

- ◆ **Financial Growth:**

The revenue generated by the sale or lease of the self-sustainable house will increase the company's overall income, while the shorter payback period (3-4 years) will improve cash flow. Additionally, by reducing long-term operational costs through sustainable systems, the company will significantly reduce future maintenance costs and enhance profitability.

- ◆ **Human Resources Development:**

With the completion of this project, the company will gain valuable expertise in sustainable construction, which can be leveraged in future projects. The specialized staff hired for this project will form a core team for future self-sustainable developments, enhancing the company's talent pool and creating opportunities for growth and innovation within the organization.

- ◆ **Market Expansion and Customer Loyalty:**

As more people become aware of the benefits of self-sustainable living, the market for eco-friendly homes will expand. The company will be able to capitalize on this trend by offering additional self-sustainable houses, thus increasing market share. The project will also attract environmentally conscious customers who value long-term cost savings and sustainability, fostering greater customer loyalty and increasing the likelihood of repeat business and referrals.

2.4.4 Regulations

The self-sustainable house project will fully comply with Spanish national building codes, environmental regulations, and European Union (EU) standards for energy efficiency, water usage, and the use of sustainable building materials. It is important to ensure that the construction aligns with both local and EU-wide regulations that govern sustainable development.

Below are the specific codes and regulations relevant to this project:

European Union Directives

- ◆ **Energy Performance of buildings Directive (EPBD) – Directive 2018/844/EU:** This EU directive improves the energy performance of buildings across the Union. In Spain, it requires that all new buildings meet nearly zero-energy standards. The self-sustainable house will incorporate renewable energy sources and ensure high energy efficiency to comply with this directive.
- ◆ **Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) – Directive 2018/2001/EU:** The RED II directive promotes the use of renewable energy. The self-sustainable house will use solar energy and potentially other systems like wind or geothermal to align with this directive.
- ◆ **Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC):** This directive governs sustainable water usage. The self-sustainable house will integrate water-saving technologies, such as rainwater harvesting and greywater recycling, to reduce reliance on public water supplies.
- ◆ **Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC):** This regulation addresses the management and reduction of construction waste. The project will use at least 70% recycled and sustainable materials and will have a plan for managing construction waste.

Spanish National Building Codes

- ◆ **Technical Building Code (Código Técnico de la Edificación - CTE):** The CTE is Spain's primary building code, which governs all aspects of construction. Relevant sections include:
- ◆ **CTE HE – Energy Efficiency (Ahorro de Energía):** Ensures new buildings reduce energy consumption. The self-sustainable house will exceed energy efficiency requirements through passive design, insulation, and renewable energy systems.
- ◆ **CTE HS – Health and Hygiene (Salubridad):** This section governs water use and air quality. The project will include water-efficient fixtures and advanced ventilation systems.
- ◆ **Regulation on Thermal Installations in Buildings (Reglamento de Instalaciones Térmicas en los Edificios - RITE):** This regulation governs heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems in Spain. The house will minimize energy use with renewable energy-powered HVAC systems.

Environmental Regulations

- ◆ **Environmental Impact Assessment Law (Ley de Evaluación Ambiental):** This law requires an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) for construction projects. A thorough EIA will be conducted to minimize environmental impacts, such as carbon emissions or resource depletion.
- ◆ **Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima - PNIEC) 2021-2030:** The project will align with Spain's national goals to reduce carbon emissions and increase the use of renewable energy, as outlined in the PNIEC.

Sustainable Construction Materials Standards

- ◆ **Construction Products Regulation (Reglamento de Productos de la Construcción - Regulation (EU) No 305/2011):** This EU regulation ensures construction materials meet safety, health, and environmental standards. The project will use materials with the CE marking to verify compliance.
- ◆ **ISO 14001 – Environmental Management Systems:** While voluntary, this standard provides guidelines for minimizing environmental impact.
- ◆ The project will aim to follow ISO 14001 for responsible construction practices.

Fire and Safety Regulations

- ◆ **CTE Fire Safety (Seguridad en caso de Incendio - DB-SI):** Fire safety is governed by the CTE's fire safety section (DB-SI). The self-sustainable house will use fire-resistant materials and plan evacuation routes according to this regulation.
- ◆ **Insulation and Thermal Performance Standards**
- ◆ **ISO 10456 – Thermal Insulation Standards:** To meet high energy efficiency standards, ISO 10456 provides guidance on thermal insulation for building materials. This will help select materials that reduce heat loss and improve the house's energy efficiency.

3. Definition of the Project

3.1 General Description of the Project

General Description
An innovative self- sustainable housing design called "ECO-Housing" avoids the need for homes to be connected to the public utilities system. By utilizing smart home technologies, water harvesting, renewable energy sources, recyclable materials, and innovative construction techniques, we can build a conventional house that is totally off the grid in terms of supplies. Moreover, the primary goal is to complete all construction within a maximum of 12 months and at a maximum cost of 500.000 euros.
Scope
Design and building of a self-sustainable house, using the most eco and state of the art technologies. Different natural and physics principles will need to be put into practice in order not to be connected to public supplies, covering up water recycling and harvesting systems, renewable energy and climate systems.
Cost
500.000 €
Time
12 months
Project goal and objectives
<p>◆ Project goal:</p> <p>Mainly, the design and construction of the house, using advanced technology and systems to achieve sustainability and utilities self-sufficiency. All these steps will need to be taken on time, considering all the internal and external issues that may arise (regulations, legal requirements, maintenance...) as the project goes through.</p> <p>◆ Project objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Build the house and implement its systems within 12 months.2. The total investment cost should be within the range of 500.000 € of the project budget.3. Construct a house using at least 70% of materials that are sustainable and recyclable.4. Reduce construction waste by 60% through recycling and reuse practices.

Product Objectives
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Construct a house with water self-sufficiency of 40% and above. 2. Construct a house using at least 70% of materials that are sustainable and recyclable. 3. Maintain a comfortable indoor temperature (between 20-25°C) without excessive use of heating or cooling systems. 4. Construct a house with an energy self-sufficiency of 50% and above.
Assumptions
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Legal compliance with local city councils and sustainability regulations and laws will not change during the project course. 2. Materials will be available within the local areas, avoiding procurement problems and delays in the construction process. 3. The team will have previous knowledge or experience in sustainability or well related to it in terms of renewable sources and new systems. 4. All the machinery needed for the construction of a self-sustainable house will be available. 5. Environmentally balanced in terms carbon footprint, developing a positive impact on the construction. 6. Technology and sustainable systems will be available for the construction 7. Favorable weather conditions will be suitable for construction and will not cause significant delays or damage to any of the stages. 8. Supplier standards are defined and follow the strategy of the company.
Constrains
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The project will not exceed the 500.000 € budget. 2. The construction will be done within 12 months' time from the starting day 3. The sustainable materials and technologies needed must be available and delivered on time. 4. The project must accomplish all the legal requirements involved in new sustainable constructions and buildings. 5. Keep the high standards in quality and sustainability as specified all the different phases of the project.

Table 3: General Description of the Project

3.2 SWOT/PREN Analysis

Organizations and people utilize the SWOT function, a strategic planning tool, to emphasize the important elements that can affect success and direct decision-making. The following chart shows the different aspects and current situations that can make the project successful or where to focus to keep control of the weakest parts.

Illustration 8: SWOT Analysis (own creation)

In a similar way, the PREN analysis helps to understand the different society aspects that can affect our project regarding the construction sector, as shown below.

Illustration 9: PREN Analysis (own creation)

3.3 Critical Success Factors (CSFs)

The key areas that must be properly managed to ensure the project's success are what we understand for critical success factors. Some examples are shown below, keeping in mind that the house needs to achieve all the sustainability standards mentioned as well as the condition to remain comfortable and modern at the same time.

Objectives	CSF	Component of the CSF	Actions and Resources
Develop the project aligned with the 500.000€ budget	Avoid overruns and extra costs in any of the stages of the project, especially on the execution part	Follow the financial planning as well as the budget control in each and every milestone.	Cost saving resources, crowdfunding for investors and money and a well-managed budget control should be enough tools to keep its objective.
Complete the project in 12 months	Deliver the project (the building) within the time planned and defined from the beginning	Manage the timeline and milestones and emphasize on the critical parts of the project to develop them on time	Develop an accurate schedule planning leaving room for possible buffers that may arise
Develop a full timeline and schedule plan to finish all the stages of the project as established	Establish a completed schedule that includes all the phases of the project		Structure and manage a schedule plan considering all the tasks and phases of the project
Keep the workers safe	Ensure the safety of all the workers involved in the project, paying extra attention on the construction part	Define a quality and risk plan which ensures a safe environment for internal and external contractors and workers	Develop a safety plan and communicate with the HSE Supervisor to coordinate and manage the critical stages of the project

Reduce energy waste and become self-sustainable	Generate at least 80% of the required energy from renewable sources systems	Design the building taking into account location, orientation and the newest sustainable systems in order to become self-sustainable	Install and build the construction with the latest sustainable and efficient systems in terms of general supplies (electricity, water and waste recycling)
Get the sustainable certifications with the highest score	Achieve a high ranking in BREEAM, which measures the environmental performance of the buildings	Focus on the renewable and sustainable systems and local suppliers to make the logistics more ecofriendly too	Plan and execute, together with the legal team, a roadmap to accomplish and get all the legal requirements and compliance in order to achieve the best score
Lower the energy consumption around 50% annually compared to a traditional house	Achieve an annual energy consumption that is at least 50% lower than the traditional buildings	Combine sustainable architecture and renewable resources consultants to build up net zero consumption	Implement systems that use renewable energies or resources to reduce the consumption

Table 4: Critical Success Factors (CSF's)

3.4 Alternative Scenario

The following criteria has been defined to analyze the possible alternative scenarios:

Criteria	Act on	Weight
Cost	Reduce or increase the cost of the project	30%
Time	Reduce or increase the execution of the project	20%
Quality	Ensure the quality standards defined	30%
Risk	Increase or reduce the risk	20%
TOTAL		100%

Table 5: Alternative Scenarios Analysis

The score defined by the high-level management will be a 1-5 range, where 5 will mean a better performance or importance. The next cases will be debated as alternatives:

1. High technology and half public supplied house (not full self-sustainable).

- ◆ **Cost:** the investment in equipment and the best technology systems would increase significantly the price for the whole building.
- ◆ **Time:** will take more time to develop the electrical supplies and will make it more difficult rather than other known systems.
- ◆ **Quality:** would provide the best quality possible and upgrades the standard planned initially but not would end up not being fully sustainable.
- ◆ **Risk:** potential risks arise when quality improves.

Criteria	Weight	Self-sustainable medium quality	High quality with on-grid systems
Cost	35%	4	1
Time	15%	4	4
Quality	35%	3	5
Risk	15%	3	2
TOTAL	100%	3,5	3

Table 6: Alternative Scenario 1

2. Outsource the construction part to a professional construction company

- ◆ **Cost:** might be better cause the big construction companies may have deals and communications with suppliers.
- ◆ **Time:** better and new building equipment turns out to be faster than ordinary tools and machinery.
- ◆ **Quality:** might be compromised as the fast-paced concept might affect to quality instead
- ◆ **Risk:** many projects at a time involve some more risks than one after one.

Criteria	Weight	Outsourced	Self-built
Cost	30%	4	2
Time	20%	4	3
Quality	30%	3	4
Risk	20%	3	2
TOTAL	100%	3,5	2,8

Table 7: Alternative Scenario 2

3. Self-sustainable traditional house

- ◆ **Cost:** more competitive than with modern and smart sustainable technologies built to manage the resources and how to manage them
- ◆ **Time:** might be slightly different but it also takes time and some more long processes made traditionally.
- ◆ **Quality:** will be simple and not providing the high-quality standards defined in the plan
- ◆ **Risk:** can affect socially as might not be seen as a revolutionary construction concept

Criteria	Weight	Traditional	Modern
Cost	20%	4	3
Time	20%	3	3
Quality	35%	3	4
Risk	25%	3	4
TOTAL	100%	3,2	3,6

Table 8: Alternative Scenario 3

Results and Conclusions

Criteria	Quality Rate	Outsource construction	Type of construction
Mark	3,5 - 3	3,5 -2,8	3,2 - 3,6
Total	3,5	3,5	3,6

Having considered different scenarios and ongoing alternative analysis it becomes quite clear that the main structure and construction of the building could be outsourced to optimize resources and costs. However, if this path would be taken, it'd be strongly supervised from one specialized team that would define all the main aspects of the construction and the different kinds of materials and systems to be implemented. That would minimize the possibility of delivering lower quality or results that could appear when not being built by ECO - Housing.

3.5 Stakeholder Analysis

Internal Stakeholders

Stakeholder	Analysis
CEO	Person in charge of the overview and well-development of the project.
Sponsor	Individual or company supporting the project financially but also in terms of authority and strongly related with the high-level stakeholders and key decisions.
Project Manager	Responsible for the management of the plans and structure of all the project. Needs to coordinate and manage all the activities in order to reach the deadlines within the planned budget.
Sustainability Architect	Responsible for the main design and sustainability principles from the construction. In charge of the distribution and comfort of the ongoing building, always respecting the local regulations and legal compliance.
Civil Engineer	Takes care of the structure and its materials, developing a durable and sustainable body for the house, that will be strongly bonded to the architect in order to find the best sustainable solutions.
Renewable Energy Engineer	Designated to build and research on the best energetic systems for the house. In charge of all the supplies including water, electricity and climate. Needs to ensure the house can be run off-grid.
Procurement Manager	Manage the main material suppliers as well as tech systems for the smart house. Need to ensure the right time delivery for the resources with no delay or suppliers issues.
Construction Team	Takes part in the entire construction process, coordinating between different teams and ensuring the project stays on schedule and within budget.
Quality Manager	Develop regular reports and analysis that ensure the construction meets the standards of sustainability and quality established on the plan.
Legal Manager	Develop the strategical plan to accomplish with the current laws and requirements such as council licenses, construction licenses. Also in charge of the requirements coming from the certifications needed.
Health and Safety Supervisor	Responsible for the well-being of each and every member or contractor involved in the construction. Ensures the correct procedures and supervises the environmental part as well.

Table 9: Internal Stakeholder Analysis

External Stakeholders

Stakeholder	Analysis
Suppliers	Responsible for providing a wide range of materials. They have a direct impact on the quality, logistics and timing of the construction project.
Neighbors and local community	Have a strong power among the place and can be a big ally or the worst enemy. Need to keep them posted, engage in the project and communicate regularly with them.
Clients	Play one of the most important parts of the project as they need to invest in a 'new building concept'. Although it is a future and sustainable idea, the initial spending can make them step back if things go sideways and they're not under control.
Construction Team	Takes part in the entire construction process, coordinating between different teams and ensuring the project stays on schedule and within budget.
Local Council	Depending on the role they play against green building concept and new sustainable technologies there will be a strong bond and communication for legal requirements and licenses.

Table 10: External Stakeholder Analysis

P/I Matrix

Stakeholder	Power (1 to 5)	Interest (1 to 5)
CEO	5	4
Sponsor	5	5
Project Manager	4	4
Sustainability Architect	3	3
Civil Engineer	3	3
Legal Manager	4	4
Renewable Energy Engineer	4	3
Procurement	2	3
Construction Team	2	3
Quality Inspector	1	3
Health and Safety Supervisor	3	4
Suppliers	2	2
Neighbors and local community	3	2
Clients	3	5
Local authorities and Governments	4	2

Table 11: P/I Matrix

Illustration 10: Power/Interest Matrix

Saliency Model

According to the stakeholders mentioned above, the following chart has been developed based on the influence or importance, the legitimacy and the urgency it may have on the different tasks and activities.

Illustration 11: Saliency Model

4. Project Charter

Name of the Project
Self-sustainable House Project
Project Purpose or Justification
<p>The purpose of this project is the design and construction of a self-sustainable house in Sant Vicenç dels Horts to reduce the environmental impact using environmentally friendly materials, renewable energy and construction techniques that minimize the carbon footprint. The project's primary goal is the design and construction of a self-sufficient utility house that consumes less energy, using technologies such as solar panels, rainwater harvesting systems and efficient thermal insulation. It will also have other secondary goals such as economic savings by reducing long-term costs associated with energy and water consumption as well as maintenance expenses thanks to the durability and efficiency of the materials and systems used.</p> <p>Furthermore, the project aims to improve the quality of life of the inhabitants through the use of non-toxic materials, better indoor air quality and a design that maximizes natural light and thermal comfort.</p> <p>By achieving all the commented points, the project will promote innovation in construction techniques and serve as an educational model for future sustainable construction.</p> <p>The justification of ECO - Housing is helping improve environmental impact. By using renewable energy sources, eco-friendly materials, and innovative construction techniques, the company will be able to reduce the carbon footprint and environmental impact. This project aligns with global sustainability goals and demonstrates a commitment to the environment, making it a worthy investment. The company will comply with environmental regulations, avoiding fines and penalties. Sustainable companies are viewed more positively by consumers, enhancing their reputation. Sustainability innovation can provide a competitive advantage by adopting cleaner technologies and practices. External investors and financial institutions are increasingly interested in supporting sustainable projects.</p>

Measurable Project Objectives and Related Success Criteria

<p>Objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Construct a house with an energy self-sufficiency of 50% and above. 2. Construct a house with water self-sufficiency of 40% and above. 3. Construct a house using at least 70% of materials that are sustainable and recyclable. 4. Maintain a comfortable indoor temperature (between 20-25°C) without excessive use of heating or cooling systems. 5. Reduce construction waste by 60% through recycling and reuse practices. 	<p>CSF:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop this project with a budget of 500.000 €. 2. Complete the project in 12 months and make the final delivery on 01.09.2025. 3. Establish a completed schedule that includes all the phases of the project. 4. Define a quality and risk plan which ensures a safe environment for the workers. 5. Generate at least 80% of the required energy from renewable sources installed on the property. 6. Achieve a high rating in the BREEAM, which measures the environmental performance of buildings. 7. Achieve an annual energy consumption that is at least 50% lower than that of a conventional home.
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High-Level Requirements:

(need to be considered before executing the project)

- ◆ **Renewable Energy Integration:** Incorporate solar panels, wind turbines, and other renewable energy generation systems.
- ◆ **House Orientation:** Optimize the orientation of the house to maximize natural light and ventilation.
- ◆ **Thermal Insulation:** Use high efficiency materials for insulation of walls, ceilings and floors.
- ◆ **Rainwater Harvesting and water recycling:** Implement systems to collect and store rainwater for irrigation and other non-potable purposes. Install systems for the treatment and reuse of greywater in the home.

- ◆ **Sustainable Building Materials:** Use recycled, recyclable and low environmental impact materials. Ensure that the materials used have certifications that guarantee their sustainability.
- ◆ **Comfort and Well-Being:** Ensure that housing design promotes comfort and ergonomics for inhabitants. Incorporate green areas and gardens to improve well-being and connection with nature.
- ◆ **Regulatory Compliance:** Ensure that the project complies with all local building and sustainability rules and regulations and obtain all necessary certifications and permits required for construction and operation of the home.
- ◆ **Supplier Management:** Establish agreements and contracts with suppliers specializing in sustainable materials and technologies. This includes coordinating deliveries, ensuring the quality of materials and services, and managing any issues that arise during the construction process.
- ◆ **Budget Planning and Management:** Develop and maintain a detailed budget covering all aspects of the project, from materials procurement to labor and regulatory compliance costs. Monitor and adjust the budget as necessary to avoid cost overruns and ensure efficient allocation of financial resources.
- ◆ These high-level requirements provide an initial framework for designing and constructing a self-sustainable house.

High-Level Project Description, Boundaries and Key Deliverables

- ◆ **Project Description:** ECO - Housing is a project that aims to successfully design and create a self-sustainable house in the country of Spain. The project will focus on designing and building a self-sustainable house that minimizes environmental impact, maximizes energy efficiency and promotes the well-being of its inhabitants. This project will serve as a model for innovation in sustainable construction.
- ◆ **Project Boundaries:** The project boundaries define the scope and limitations of ECO - Housing. This can include aspects such as:
 - ◆ **High technologies Costs:** Investment for sustainable technologies, such as solar panels, water harvesting systems, and green materials, can be considerably high.
 - ◆ **Availability of Materials:** Not all sustainable materials are readily available in all regions, which may delay the project or increase transportation costs.
 - ◆ **Regulations and Permits:** Local building regulations may not be up to date for sustainable projects, which can complicate permitting.

- ◆ **Climatic and Geographic Conditions:** Site-specific climatic and geographic conditions may limit the effectiveness of certain sustainable technologies, such as solar or wind energy.
- ◆ **Maintenance and Operation:** Sustainable systems may require specialized and regular maintenance, which can be costly and complicated.
- ◆ **Technological Innovation:** Rapid evolution of sustainable technologies may make some solutions obsolete quickly.
- ◆ **Key Deliverable Elements:**
 - ◆ **Architectural drawings:** Detailed designs that include the use of sustainable materials and passive construction techniques.
 - ◆ **Feasibility report:** Analysis demonstrating the technical and economic feasibility of the project.
 - ◆ **Renewable energy system:** Installation and configuration of solar panels, wind turbines or other renewable energy sources.
 - ◆ **Rainwater harvesting system:** Design and implementation of systems to collect and reuse rainwater.
 - ◆ **Energy efficiency systems:** Installation of energy-efficient lighting systems, as well as thermal insulation.
 - ◆ **Warranties and Maintenance Contracts:** Provide all warranties for installed equipment (solar panels, water collection systems, efficient appliances, etc.). Provide information on existing maintenance contracts and recommendations for future services.
 - ◆ **Registrations and Certifications:** Provide copies of all certifications obtained (LEED, BREEAM).
 - ◆ **Contacts and Resources:** Provide a contact list of suppliers, contractors, and specialized technicians who participated in the project.
 - ◆ **Final Evaluation Report:** Provide a detailed report evaluating the project's performance in terms of sustainability, energy efficiency, and meeting objectives.

Profile of the team

- ◆ **CEO:**

Responsibilities: Define the vision of the project, oversee the finances, generate engagement with the stakeholders, monitor the progress of the project and mitigate risks to achieve project goals.

◆ **Sponsor:**

Responsibilities: Ensuring the project aligns with the organization's strategic goals and objectives, approving all the necessary funding and resources for the project. Monitoring the project's progress and supporting the project manager in overcoming obstacles.

◆ **Project Manager:**

Responsibilities: Oversees the entire ECO - Housing project, coordinates activities, manages timelines and budgets, and ensures project goals are achieved.

◆ **Sustainability Architect:**

Responsibilities: Design the house with sustainability principles, optimizing orientation, natural light and ventilation. Select eco-friendly materials and ensure that the design complies with sustainability regulations.

◆ **Civil Engineer:**

Responsibilities: Oversee the structure of the house, ensuring it is safe and durable. Collaborate with the architect to integrate sustainable solutions into the structure.

◆ **Renewable Energy Engineer:**

Responsibilities: Design and implement renewable energy systems, such as solar panels, wind turbines, water collection and recycling systems. Ensure energy efficiency of housing.

◆ **Procurement Manager:**

Responsibilities: Manage subcontractors and suppliers ensuring that deadlines and budget are met.

◆ **Construction Team:**

Responsibilities: Construction of the building, installations of the renewable sustainable systems and collaborate closely with other professionals to integrate eco-friendly practices throughout the project.

◆ **Quality Manager:**

Responsibilities: Perform periodic inspections to ensure construction meets established quality and sustainability standards.

◆ **Legal Manager:**

Responsibilities: Ensuring the project complies with all applicable laws, regulations, and policies. Identifying and mitigating legal risks associated with the project.

◆ **Health and Safety Supervisor:**

Responsibilities: Developing, implementing, and enforcing safety protocols and procedures and ensuring the project team is prepared for emergencies and has the necessary plans and equipment.

Key stakeholder list

Internal:

CEO

Sponsor

Project manager

Sustainability Architect

Civil Engineer

Renewable Energy Engineer

Procurement Manager

Construction Team

Quality Manager

Legal Manager

Health and Safety Supervisor

External:

Suppliers

Neighbors and local community

Clients

Construction Team

Local Council

Overall project risk

Financial Risk

Materials Availability Risk

Regulatory Risk

Cost Control Risk

Technical Risk

Climate and Geographic Risk

Knowledge Risk

Operation Risk

Assumptions

- 1. Availability of Sustainable Materials:** Sustainable and recycled materials needed for construction will be available in the local market or can be procured without significant delays.
- 2. Regulatory Compliance:** Local and national building and sustainability regulations will not change significantly during the course of the project, allowing design and construction to proceed as planned.
- 3. Favorable Weather Conditions:** Weather conditions will be suitable for construction and will not cause significant delays or damage to materials or structures.
- 4. Technology Availability:** Technologies needed for energy efficiency and sustainability (such as solar panels, water harvesting systems) will be available and will perform as expected.
- 5. Environmental Impact:** The environmental impact of the project will be positive, contributing to the reduction of the carbon footprint and promoting sustainable practices in the community.
- 6. Staff Training:** The construction team and technicians will be adequately trained and experienced to implement sustainable techniques and technologies.
- 7. Machinery:** All the machinery needed for the construction will be available.
- 8. Supplier standards:** Suppliers standards are known and defined following the strategy of the company.

Constraints

1. The total budget of 500 thousand euros should cover all project costs, including design, materials, labor, sustainable technologies and contingencies.
2. The project must be completed within 12 months, from start of construction to completion and handover.
3. The necessary sustainable materials and technologies must be available and delivered on time.
4. The project must comply with all local and national building and sustainability regulations.
5. Maintain high standards of quality and sustainability within the established budget and timeframe.

Pre-Approved Financial Resources

The total budget is 500 thousand euros. This should cover all project costs, including design, materials, labor, sustainable technologies and contingencies.

Summary Milestone Schedule

Initiation & Planning

Project Definition Finished: 10.10.2024

End of Initiation and Planning: 12.11.2024

Kick Off Meeting: 14.11.2024

Execution

Design Completion: 15.01.2025

Obtaining construction licenses and permits: 24.01.2025

Suppliers validated and materials tested: 21.03.2025

Construction initiation: 24.03.2025

Foundations Completed: 21.04.2025

Building construction Completed: 24.07.2025

Installation of Sustainable Systems: 07.08.2025

Monitoring and Controlling

Report with feedback of participants: 15.08.2025

Closure

Project Closure: 01.09.2025

Project Approval Requirements

Who decides that the project is successful

- CEO
- Sponsor
- Project Manager
- Civil Engineer

Who signs off the project

The project initiation & planning is approved by the CEO, Sponsor, PM and the Civil Engineer when the project management plan is complete.

Resources are approved by the project manager when a sustainable architect, renewable energy engineer and procurement have been secured.

Law and regulatory compliance are approved by the sustainable architect, environmental consultant and quality Inspector.

Budget and funding justification is approved by the CEO, Sponsor and PM when all the estimates have been addressed on the project management plan.

Risk assessment and mitigation Plan approved by Project Manager when all the possible risks have been gathered from the project team.

All contracts are approved by the legal department & board of directors.

The project closure will be approved by the CEO, Sponsor, Civil Engineer and Project Manager when the project is completed.

Project Exit Criteria

The project cost exceeds the maximum budget by 10%.

The project duration exceeds the scheduled duration by 20%.

The project does not comply with regulations and laws.

The architectural and structural designs are not feasible.

If qualitative parameters are not met.

Assigned Project Manager, Responsibility, and Authority Level

ECO - Housing design and construction project needs experienced people to lead the project so that it can meet the triple constraint.

After the discussion of the team, it was decided that Ana Rodriguez will be the project manager of this project. Ana Rodriguez has professional knowledge in construction, good communication skills and can coordinate and integrate resources from all parties.

Name and Authority of the Sponsor or other person(s) authorizing the project charter

Name/Position

Laura Martinez/ CEO, Carlos Gomez/ Sponsor, Sara Fernandez/ Civil Engineer, Ana Rodríguez/ Project Manager

Table 12: Project Charter (own creation)

5. Planning of the Project

5.1 Stakeholder Plan

A stakeholder management plan will be designed for this project to ensure effective engagement of all stakeholders and analyze the relationships and conflicts among them. Finally, an action plan will be developed to determine the positioning of key stakeholders.

5.1.1 Stakeholder analysis

The project management team will complete a stakeholder analysis matrix to display the concerns, impact, influence, requirements, and management strategies for each stakeholder.

Stakeholder	Concerns	Impact	Influence	Requirements	Strategy
CEO	Project success and ROI	High	High	Regular updates, risk management and strategic alignment	Keep a high-level engagement and regular briefings. Get involve in key decisions.
Sponsor	Project strategic goals and objectives. Necessary funding's and resources	High	High	Regular updates, risk management and strategic alignment	Keep a high-level engagement and regular briefings. Get involve in key decisions.

Stakeholder	Concerns	Impact	Influence	Requirements	Strategy
Project Manager	Project timeline, budget, scope and resource allocation	High	High	Clear objectives, resource availability, support from stakeholders	Maintain regular meetings. Use clear communication channels and support in conflict resolution
Sustainability Architect	Environmental impact, design feasibility, innovation	Medium	Medium	Access to latest sustainable materials, collaborate with engineers	Get involved in construction decisions. Provide necessary resources and encourage innovation
Civil Engineer	Structural integrity, compliance with standards, project feasibility	High	Medium	Create detailed plans and drawings. Collaborate with other engineers	Maintain regular technical meetings and get involved to support in problem-solving
Renewable Energy Engineer	Integration of renewable energy systems, efficiency, cost-effectiveness	Medium	Medium	Access to project plans and drawings. Collaborate with other engineers	Get involved in early planning stages and regular updates. Complete alignment with sustainability goals
Procurement Manager	Cost control, timely delivery of materials, supplier reliability	Medium	Medium	Have clear view on specifications, time and budget constraints	Get involved in regular updates on project needs ensuring a good supplier relationships
Construction Team	Have all the material and machinery to be able to carry out the project	Medium	Low	Access to project plans and drawings. Collaborate with other teams. Have clear	Get involved in early planning stages and regular updates. Maintain regular technical meetings.

Stakeholder	Concerns	Impact	Influence	Requirements	Strategy
				view on specifications and time.	
Quality Manager	Compliance with quality standards, safety, project specifications	Medium	Low	Access to project plans and drawings. Attend to inspections and cooperate with the team	Make regular inspections using the company standards and showing a fast resolution of issues
Legal Manager	Review applicable laws, regulations and policies.	High	High	Have clear view on project specifications. Access to the newest laws, regulations and subsidies. Collaborate with engineers.	Get involved in initial project planning meetings to understand the project scope, objectives, and potential legal implications. Ensure the Legal Manager is aware of all key stakeholders and their roles.
Health and Safety Supervisor	Ensure safety practices among the workers.	High	Medium	Knowledge on specific safety requirements and standards of the construction industry.	Schedule regular meetings to discuss safety issues, review incident reports, and update safety protocols. Define the Health and Safety Supervisor's responsibilities and ensuring a safety workplace.

Stakeholder	Concerns	Impact	Influence	Requirements	Strategy
Suppliers	Payment terms, delivery schedules, long-term relationship	Medium	Low	Clear contracts, respect timely payments and supply regular orders	Maintain good communication, ensure timely payments and build a long-term partnerships
Neighbors and local Community	Noise, environmental impact, benefits to community	Low	Medium	Get information on project timeline and community benefits	Make community meetings, address concerns as fast as possible and highlight community benefits
Clients	Project quality, timeline, cost, sustainability features	High	High	Regular updates, involvement in key decisions, transparency	Regular progress reports, involve in decision-making, ensure clear communication
Local Council	Compliance with regulations and environmental impact	High	High	Detailed project plans and drawings. Ensure compliance reports	Get informed on regulatory updates. Ensure compliance with regulations and get involved in community engagement efforts

Table 13: Stakeholder Analysis

Updated P/I matrix

Stakeholder	Power (1 to 5)	Interest (1 to 5)
CEO	5	4
Sponsor	5	5
Project Manager	4	4
Sustainability Architect	3	3
Legal Manager	4	4
Civil Engineer	3	3
Renewable Energy Engineer	4	3
Procurement	2	3
Construction Team	2	3
Quality Inspector	1	3
Health and Safety Supervisor	3	4
Suppliers	2	2
Neighbors and local community	3	2
Clients	3	5
Local authorities and Governments	4	2

Table 14: Updated P/I Matrix

Illustration 12: P/I Matrix

5.1.2 Action Plan

Stakeholder	Actions
CEO	Schedule monthly regular high-level meetings to provide detailed progress reports and get involved in strategic decision-making.
Sponsor	Schedule monthly regular high-level meetings to clearly outline the goals and expectations of the project. Discuss and finalize the budget, ensuring it aligns with the sponsor’s financial expectations. Establish a realistic timeline for project milestones and completion.
Project Manager	Conduct weekly project meetings to review progress, address issues, and plan upcoming tasks with each of the stakeholders. Ensure clear communication channels are established and maintained among all team members and stakeholders. Provide support in conflict resolution and decision-making to keep the project on track.
Sustainability Architect	<p>Involve the sustainability architect in all construction decisions to ensure environmental considerations are integrated from the start. Provide access to the latest sustainable materials and technologies to support innovative construction solutions.</p> <p>Encourage the architect to propose and implement the best and newest sustainable practices.</p>
Civil Engineer	<p>Hold regular technical meetings to discuss structural plans, compliance issues, and construction challenges.</p> <p>Facilitate the necessary information, such as detailed architectural plans, drawings and engineering specifications.</p> <p>Support the civil engineer in problem-solving and decision-making processes to address any technical issues that arise.</p>

Renewable Energy Engineer	<p>Involve the renewable energy engineer in the early planning stages to facilitate the integration of renewable energy systems effectively. Provide regular updates on project progress and any changes that may impact energy system design.</p> <p>Ensure alignment with sustainability goals by coordinating closely with the sustainability architect.</p>
Procurement Manager	<p>Give the feedback on project needs and procurement actions to ensure timely delivery of materials.</p> <p>Establish procurement processes and communicate them to all relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>Maintain strong relationships with suppliers to ensure reliability and quality of materials.</p>
Construction Team	<p>Collaborate in the selection of sustainable materials. Implement efficient construction practices, install renewable energy and water management systems. Ensure the house meets sustainability standards and performs optimally.</p>
Quality Manager	<p>Make regular inspections to ensure compliance with quality standards and project specifications.</p> <p>Communicate the quality standards and expectations to the construction team.</p> <p>Address any quality issues as soon as that arise and implement corrective actions.</p>
Legal Manager	<p>Keep all stakeholders informed about legal requirements and any changes in regulations. Verify that the project complies with local laws and regulation. Identify potential legal risks and develop strategies to mitigate them. Identify possible subsidies that can relate with the project.</p>
Health and Safety Supervisor	<p>Keep all stakeholders informed about health and safety measures. Ensure compliance with local, state, and national health and safety regulations and Create plans to mitigate risks and ensure workers safety.</p>
Suppliers	<p>Maintain a good communication with the suppliers to ensure that they understand the project requirements and timings.</p>

	<p>Ensure prompt payments to suppliers to maintain a good relationships and avoid delays.</p> <p>Build a long-term partnerships with the company key suppliers to secure reliable and high-quality materials.</p>
Neighbors and local Community	<p>Update the neighbors on the project progress, timings, and any potential changes.</p> <p>Hold community meetings to gather feedback and now perspectives from local residents.</p> <p>Highlight the benefits of the project to the community, such as improved sustainability and potential economic benefits.</p>
Clients	<p>Communicate the status and changes on the project to our clients.</p> <p>Involve clients in key decision-making processes to ensure their needs and expectations are met.</p> <p>Promote transparent communication to build trust and confidence with the customers.</p>
Local Council	<p>Provide the latest updates on the project progress and compliance with the regulations.</p> <p>Ensure all necessary permits and approvals are obtained on time.</p> <p>Involve local authorities to demonstrate the project’s benefits and compliance.</p>

Table 15: Action Plan

5.2 Communications Management Plan

This communications management plan is important for the success of the Self-sustainable House project. It sets the framework for communication throughout the project, highlighting the information flow among stakeholders. The plan serves as a guide to ensure shared information is clear, timely and consistent throughout the project lifecycle. One of the plan's main goals is to ensure that the project's identified stakeholders are effectively informed about the project objectives, progress, issues, and changes. It helps establish communication guidelines, channels, and schedules that affect collaboration. This concisely defines communication methods, frequency, responsible parties, and escalation procedures to facilitate stakeholder collaboration and eliminate misunderstanding. It helps keep stakeholders informed and address issues efficiently, serving as a reference for how and when stakeholders will receive critical information.

5.2.1 Communication Strategy

The communication strategy focuses on maintaining transparency, promoting collaboration, and ensuring all project members understand their roles and contributions. The Project Manager will take a proactive role in ensuring effective communication on this project. The communications requirements are documented in the Communications Matrix presented in this document. The Communications Matrix will be used as the guide for what information to communicate, who is to do the communication, when to communicate it and to whom to communicate. As with other plans, changes and updates in the communication plan may be required as the project progresses. The project manager is responsible for managing all proposed and approved changes to the communication plan. The approved changes and updates to the plan and supporting document will be effectively transmitted to all relevant project teams and stakeholders.

Key communication objectives:

- ◆ Foster open and transparent communication.
- ◆ Ensure clarity of project objectives, progress, and challenges.
- ◆ Facilitate smooth collaboration across teams and stakeholders.
- ◆ Address and resolve issues swiftly through clear escalation processes.

Communication Constraints

With no exception, the communication activities for this project are constrained to the approved budget, schedule, resource allocations and relevant stakeholders. Communication activities will occur in accordance with the frequencies detailed in the Communication Matrix to ensure the project adheres to schedule and budgetary constraints.

EcoBuild Solution's organizational policy provides that standardized format, and template is used for all formal project communications. The details of these policy requirements are provided in the Communication Standard in this document. Similarly, the CEO or other higher-level employee may authorize the distribution of confidential information appropriately. The project manager is responsible for ensuring that approval is requested and obtained before distributing any confidential information regarding this project.

5.2.2 Stakeholder Communication Requirements

Part of the project manager's responsibilities regarding communication is the identification of appropriate project stakeholders to determine their preferred frequency and method of communication. The project manager publishes the feedback in the Project Stakeholder Register. Standard project communications will occur following the Communication Matrix. However, depending on the identified stakeholder communication requirements, individual communication is acceptable and within the constraints outlined for this project.

This project involves a wide range of stakeholders, and so do their communication requirements. Stakeholders have varying communication needs based on their roles, power and interests. The project manager will collaborate with stakeholders to identify their communication needs, preferences, frequency, method, and channel. The stakeholder communication needs will be recorded in the project register.

Each stakeholder group will be provided with specific communication requirements based on the needs identified:

◆ **Chief Executive Officer (CEO)**

The communication responsibilities of a CEO – a high-level executive employee, in this project involve ensuring alignment with the company's strategic vision, maintaining transparency with stakeholders, and promoting the project's sustainability goals. This includes engaging with investors, clients, and regulatory bodies through regular updates, financial reporting, and compliance communication. The CEO will lead internal communication with the leadership team, ensuring that the project stays on track, while handling crises and promoting the project's innovation and sustainability impact through public relations and media. Additionally, the CEO ensures that employees are engaged and aware of their roles while producing sustainability reports to showcase the project's contributions to environmental, social, and governance (ESG) objectives.

◆ **Sponsor**

The project sponsor is the promoter of the project within the organization. He has the authority to sign-off the project charter giving the legitimacy of the project manager. This person is responsible for the funding of the project and is responsible for its success. Since the project sponsor is at the executive level, communications will be presented in summary format unless he requests a more detailed version. A monthly report on the project's progress, key milestones, risks, and financial aspects will be required by the sponsor. This will be done through formal methods including in-person or virtual meetings.

◆ **Project Manager**

The project manager has the overall responsibility for the project execution. He manages everyday resources, provides project guidance and monitors and reports on the projects metrics as defined in the Project Management Plan. As the person responsible for the execution of the project, the project manager is the primary communicator for the project distributing information according to this communications management plan.

◆ **Technical Team**

The technical team members are persons in the project designated with responsibility for ensuring that technical aspects of the project are addressed and that the project is implemented in a technically sound manner. The technical team members for this project include a renewable energy engineer, a civil engineer, a quality manager and a sustainability architect. The technical team is responsible for all technical designs, overseeing the implementation of the designs and

developing as-built documentation. The technical team requires close and regular communication with the Project Manager and the project team.

◆ **Project Team Members**

The Project Team is comprised of all persons who have a role performing work on the project. The project team needs clarity and understanding of the work to be completed and the framework in which the project is to be executed. Because the project team is responsible for completing the project's tasks, they played a key role in creating the Project Plan including defining its schedule and work packages. The project team requires a detailed level of communication achieved through day-to-day interactions with the project manager and other team members in addition to weekly team meetings. Daily or weekly meetings and updates on tasks, goals, and potential challenges will be done with the project teams.

◆ **Local Council**

Relevant departments from Sant Vicenç dels Hort local council are the regulatory bodies for this project. They provide updated regulatory requirements for the project to meet the quality, environmental, sustainability and safety standards. The local council provides all the necessary permits and approval for the project and requires regular updates to ensure compliance. Project updates to ensure compliance with local laws, codes, and sustainability standards will be provided to the relevant regulatory bodies as required.

◆ **Client**

This is the customer(s) who will be accepting the final deliverable of this project. They will be informed of the project status including potential impacts to the schedule for the final deliverable or the product itself. Detailed bi-weekly progress reports highlighting achievements, risks, and any budget implications will be provided to the client.

◆ **Suppliers**

Ongoing and regular communication will be maintained with suppliers and contractors regarding materials, schedules and deliverables.

Upon identification and consultation, all stakeholders need to know their roles and responsibilities within the communication flow. Table 16 outlines the roles and responsibilities of all stakeholders in this project.

Stakeholder	Role and Responsibility
<p style="text-align: center;">CEO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicates the alignment of the construction project with broader organizational goals and strategies. - Communicate corporate policies, regulations, and high-level standards that the project must adhere to. - Communicate performance expectations, review overall project progress, and ensure alignment with the organization's performance metrics. - Communicate resolutions on escalated issues that could impact the success of the project, such as resource shortages, strategic risks, or interdepartmental conflicts. - High-Level stakeholder communication with key external stakeholders, such as regulatory bodies, investors, or clients, to manage relationships and ensure alignment with corporate objectives. - Communicate final approval of the project once completed and lead post-project reviews to communicate lessons learned and performance outcomes to the wider organization.
<p style="text-align: center;">Sponsor</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicates the overall project vision, objectives, and alignment with the organization's strategic goals to the project team and key stakeholders. - Communicates approval or disapproval for key decisions related to budget, scope, and project changes, ensuring that the project stays on track in terms of time, cost, and quality. - Receive updates on high-level risks and ensure proper communication and resolution of major issues that may affect the project's success. - Communicates support for the project within the organization, helping to resolve conflicts and ensuring resources and budgets are available. - Receive high-level project reports and updates to assess overall project health and progress and provide guidance or intervention when necessary.

<p>Project Manager</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oversees all day-to-day project communications. - Communicates project status, risks, and changes to stakeholders appropriately. - Coordinate communication between different teams, stakeholders, and contractors. - Provide regular progress updates to clients, sponsors, and the project team. - Escalate issues or risks to senior management or the steering committee as needed. - Ensure all team members are well informed about the project objectives, timelines, and changes. - Facilitate key meetings such as project kick-offs, status reviews, and final project handovers. - Communicate budget status, scope changes, and resource needs to stakeholders.
<p>Sustainability Architect</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate sustainable design concepts and strategies to the project team, ensuring alignment with environmental goals and certifications. - Collaborate with the project manager, renewable energy engineers, and construction team to ensure that sustainability elements are executed based on design for energy efficiency, water management, material use. - Coordinate with clients and stakeholders to ensure that the sustainability objectives are clear and achievable. - Update the team on regulatory compliance related to sustainability requirements and any environmental impact assessments.
<p>Quality manager</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report quality control findings to the project team and stakeholders. - Provide updates on quality assurance processes and compliance with industry standards. - Communicate non-conformance issues and collaborate with the site team to resolve them.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share quality documentation, including inspection reports and audit findings. - Coordinate with suppliers to ensure materials meet required quality standards.
Civil Engineer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Liaise with the construction team to ensure that all work complies with design specifications. - Report site progress and any technical challenges to the Project Manager and Quality Manager. - Communicate updates on testing and inspections, particularly with respect to structural and safety standards. - Coordinate site inspections and communicate findings to both the construction team and quality team.
Renewable Energy Engineer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborate with the sustainability architect and design team to integrate renewable energy solutions into the building's design and construction plan. - Communicate with the construction team about the installation and testing of energy systems including solar panels. - Report system performance and energy output expectations to the project manager and client to ensure the building meets its energy efficiency targets. - Provide updates on the procurement and delivery of energy equipment and resolve any technical issues with suppliers or contractors.
Procurement Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate with suppliers to ensure timely delivery of materials and services. - Communicate order statuses, lead times, and any supply chain issues to the Project Manager and construction team. - Report on procurement timelines and cost variances to ensure alignment with the project budget and schedule.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work with the Quality Manager to ensure materials meet quality standards before acceptance. - Escalate supply delays or material quality issues to the relevant parties (Project Manager, Construction Team, etc.).
<p style="text-align: center;">Construction Team</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide daily updates on site activities, progress, and any challenges encountered. - Communicate with the site engineer and project manager regarding material needs and task completion. - Report any construction defects or quality issues to the Quality Manager. - Share feedback on schedules and potential bottlenecks or delays.
<p style="text-align: center;">Legal Manager</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicates contract terms and conditions to the project manager, procurement team, and other stakeholders ensuring that everyone understands their legal obligations, particularly related to suppliers, contractors, and service providers. - Keeps the project team informed about relevant laws, permits, and regulations, especially those concerning environmental impact, zoning laws, and sustainable building certifications (e.g., LEED, BREEAM). - Collaborates with the project manager and other stakeholders to assess legal risks and communicate potential liabilities, such as breaches of contract, environmental fines, or non-compliance with sustainability standards. - Communicates with external parties (e.g., lawyers, regulatory bodies) and internal stakeholders in the event of legal disputes or claims to ensure timely resolution and minimize project delays. - Ensure all legal documentation is in place, including permits, contracts, and compliance reports, and provide regular updates to the project manager and stakeholders.

<p>Health and Safety Supervisor</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicates health and safety protocols and guidelines to the construction team and any other personnel on-site. This includes regular updates on safe working practices and the use of protective equipment. - Shares the results of risk assessments and hazard identification with the project teams and construction workers to ensure they are aware of potential dangers and how to mitigate them. - Reports any incidents, accidents, or near-misses to the project manager and relevant stakeholders ensuring that all incidents are properly documented, and corrective measures are communicated and implemented. - Keeps the project team updated on local and national health and safety laws and ensure compliance with occupational health regulations and sustainable building practices that may affect safety (e.g., use of eco-friendly materials). - Develops and communicate emergency response plans, including evacuation procedures and first-aid protocols making sure that all personnel are aware of what to do in the event of an emergency. - Communicates the results of regular safety inspections to the project manager and construction team.
<p>Clients</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate project goals and sustainability expectations to the project team, including desired certifications. - Receive regular updates on progress, costs, and performance from the project manager and other key stakeholders. - Provide feedback on designs, sustainability features, and progress to ensure alignment with their vision and goals. - Engage in decision-making on any design changes, budget adjustments, or sustainability features that may impact the project's scope. - Participate in final project reviews and sign off on key project deliverables, especially related to energy efficiency and environmental impact.

<p>Suppliers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate and coordinate delivery schedules with the procurement manager and construction team to ensure timely supply of materials. - Communicate material specifications and compliance with sustainability requirements for eco-friendly building materials, energy-efficient equipment, to the quality manager and project team. - Report any supply chain delays or material quality issues with the project team and propose alternative solutions if needed. - Provide documentation on the sustainability certifications of the materials and products supplied.
<p>Neighbor's and Local community</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Receive updates on project timelines and construction activities that may affect the surrounding area such as noise, traffic, environmental impact. - Provide feedback on community concerns, particularly regarding environmental and social impacts, to the project team. - Engage in public consultations to ensure transparency and community support for the project's sustainability goals. - Communicate potential benefits to the local community such as improved environmental conditions, energy savings, or public green spaces.
<p>Local Council</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issue permits and approvals for construction, environmental impact, and sustainability elements (e.g., renewable energy systems, water management). - Provide the local planning standards to ensure that the project complies with local building codes, zoning regulations, and sustainability policies. - Communicate regulatory requirements to the project manager and architects to ensure compliance. - Inspect the project at key milestones to verify that the construction aligns with approved plans and sustainability objectives.

	- Provide feedback on any required changes to plans or designs to meet regulatory standards.
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Table 16: Project's Communication Roles and Responsibilities

5.2.3 Communication Channels

In addition to identifying communication preferences, stakeholder communication requirements must identify the project's communication channels and ensure that stakeholders have access to these channels. A mixture of communication channels will be deployed to share relevant information with different stakeholders depending on urgency, formality, preference and the nature of the information. The project manager will ensure that all stakeholders have the necessary access to receive project communications. The available communication channels for this project are outlined in Table 17.

SN	Channel	Type of communication	Category
1	Email	Formal/informal communication, announcements and documentation sharing	Push
2	Microsoft Project	Tracking tasks and sharing updates	Push
3	Instant Messaging and call	Quick updates and informal communication within the team.	Interactive
4	Video Conferencing e.g., Zoom, Google Meet, Teams etc.	Meetings, discussions, and stakeholder presentations when in-person meetings are not feasible.	Interactive
5	In-person meetings	Formal face-to-face critical discussions and decision-making, when possible.	Interactive
6	Project Website/Portal	A central location where information, documents, schedules, and reports are shared.	Pull/push
7	Press release and interactive session	Public interactions with the public and other relevant stakeholders appropriately.	Push

Table 17: The Project Communication Channels

Technology Tools

The following tools will be deployed in the project to facilitate efficient communication.

- ◆ **Project Management Tool:** Microsoft Project software will be used to plan, schedule, manage, and track projects. The software helps project managers and teams organize tasks, allocate resources, track progress, manage budgets, and analyze workloads.
- ◆ **Communication Platforms:** Microsoft Teams, Slack for internal communication; Email for external communication.
- ◆ **Video Conferencing Tools:** Zoom, Google Meet and Microsoft Teams will be used for virtual meetings, with stakeholders as the need arises.
- ◆ **File Sharing:** Google Drive, and SharePoint for document management and sharing.
- ◆ **Collaborative Platforms:** Miro and Google Docs for collaborative brainstorming and document editing.

Frequency of Communication

Information sharing frequency and communication differ for different stakeholders in this project. This includes meetings with executive members, project teams, ad-hoc member's stakeholder updates, etc.

- ◆ **Project Team Meetings:** Weekly meetings to review progress, address issues, and project goals alignment/realignment.
- ◆ **Stakeholder Updates:** Bi-weekly reports sessions to sponsors and clients detailing progress, risks, and upcoming milestones.
- ◆ **Executive/Steering Committee Meetings:** Monthly meetings for high-level updates, review of strategic decisions, and resolving escalated issues.
- ◆ **Ad-hoc Meetings:** As needed to address urgent matters, changes, or critical issues.

Escalation Procedure

Sometimes certain critical matters which may be difficult to resolve at the lower level arise. In the event of issues that cannot be resolved within the team or at the project manager level, the following escalation process will be followed in this project:

- ◆ **Identify the Issue:** Team members should document the specific problem, its impact, and proposed solutions.
- ◆ **Escalate to the Project Manager:** If the issue cannot be resolved internally within teams, it is escalated to the project manager for review.
- ◆ **Escalate to the Executive Committee:** If the project manager cannot resolve the issue, it is escalated to the steering committee or senior stakeholders for a resolution.
- ◆ **Document the Resolution:** All resolutions are documented and communicated to relevant parties to avoid recurrence.

5.2.4 Communication Control and Monitoring

Monitoring communication performance focuses on assessing how effectively project communications meet stakeholders' needs. The project manager is responsible for ensuring effective communication and monitoring the strategy adopted throughout the project life. Communication monitoring is critical to ensuring that information is understood in the intended way. Communication control and monitoring for this project are implemented using tools including performance, communication matrix, change and risks and forecasting (see table 18).

Control tool	How to monitor	Indicator
Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement regular feedback loops with stakeholders to assess communication clarity, timeliness and effectiveness. - Periodic reviews communication deliverables (reports, meeting minutes, emails) to ensure adherence to the communication plan and determine if the channels and frequency are working. - Define and track communication-specific KPIs, such as response time to inquiries, the percentage of meetings held as scheduled, stakeholder engagement levels, and the number of issues resolved through effective communication. 	<p>Track whether stakeholder feedback indicates delays in updates or issues in message clarity. This can be used to identify areas of improvement if communication performance issue is noticed</p>

<p>Metrics Captured in Processes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Measure attendance rates and active participation in meetings. If key stakeholders are frequently absent, it might suggest the need for improved scheduling or relevance of meetings. - Track the delivery and timeliness of regular reports. Reports that are consistently late can signal communication bottlenecks. - Monitor how quickly team members respond to emails and other forms of communication. Delays in response times can indicate a lack of clarity or poor communication flow. - Assess the accuracy and completeness of project documentation (minutes, updates, reports). Metrics like the number of errors, omissions, or misunderstandings identified during quality checks can indicate communication gaps. 	<p>If progress reports are delayed, investigate communication bottlenecks between project stakeholders. If the progress reports or tasks are often delayed, this metric can highlight inefficiencies in how communication flows between the stakeholders (e.g. suppliers and procurement manager).</p>
<p>Changes, Risks, and Issues</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regularly review a change log to ensure that all requested changes are communicated promptly to relevant stakeholders. Monitor how quickly changes are acknowledged and incorporated into project plans. - Ensure that identified risks are communicated clearly, with risk mitigation strategies discussed and approved by stakeholders. Monitor the frequency and quality of risk-related communications, especially for issues related to sustainability (e.g., sourcing eco-friendly materials or installing energy-efficient systems). 	<p>Communicate delays in tasks or material delivery to avoid project schedule disruptions. Tracking communication of this issue and its resolution ensures transparency and avoids misunderstandings.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use an issue tracking tool to capture and monitor the status of issues raised during the project. Communicate progress on resolving issues and ensure that all stakeholders are informed of any delays, impacts, or resolutions. 	
Forecasts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor communication between project manager and teams about the availability and allocation of resources. A lack of clear communication regarding resource needs or constraints can lead to inaccurate forecasting and missed deadlines. - Use communication tools like dashboards or project management software to forecast project timelines and completion rates based on the current rate of work and communication of progress. If communication is unclear or insufficient, it could skew forecasting. - Based on past communication about risks, project teams should be able to predict potential future issues. If certain risks have been flagged but communication about mitigation strategies is lacking, it can lead to underestimating the impact of those risks in future forecasts. - Predict future communication needs by analyzing trends in current communications. For example, if project meetings increase during certain phases (e.g., installation of renewable energy systems), ensure that the forecasted communication intensity matches future project needs. 	<p>Adjust forecasting for completion if site updates have been inconsistent. Analyzing current communication flows, the project manager can better predict future communication demands and adjust strategies to ensure timely updates and progress reports.</p>

Table 18: Project Communication Control and Monitoring

5.2.5 Communication Standards

A high-quality communication standard is required for this project to achieve success. This is necessary to ensure information delivery in a structured format, using appropriate language, channels, and timing, to maintain accuracy and avoid stakeholders’ misunderstandings. The following standards will be maintained throughout the project lifecycle.

- ◆ **Clarity:** All communications will be clear, concise, using common language and free from professional or social slang as much as possible.
- ◆ **Consistency:** Communications will follow a regular schedule, format and channels unless urgent need arises.
- ◆ **Formality:** Formal reports and meeting minutes will follow a structured format with clear action items and responsible parties. In informal communication due to urgency, the information will be formally documented as soon as possible.
- ◆ **Documentation:** Key communications, including decisions, progress updates, and changes, will be documented and archived in the project management system or shared drive.

5.2.6 Communication Flowchart

Creating a communication flowchart (Illustration 13) for this project helps visualize how information flows. The communication flowchart aids in the project communication providing a framework for the project stakeholders and teams to follow. However, there may be instances where communication falls outside of the flowchart, in which case additional clarification is necessary. In these situations, the Project Manager is responsible for discussing communication with the Project Sponsor or CEO to determine how to proceed.

Illustration 13: Project Communication Flowchart

5.2.7 Guidelines for Meetings

◆ **Preparation:**

Every meeting will have a documented agenda, objectives, and guidelines. These will be circulated to all participants at least 24 hours before the meeting. Stakeholders who make direct contributions and are part of the decision-making process in the project are invited to the meeting.

◆ **Time Management:**

A specific time will be set for each meeting, ensuring the start and end times respect participants’ schedules. Participants will be allowed similar time slots to contribute to the meetings.

◆ **Participation Active:**

Participation will be encouraged for all relevant team members and stakeholders to participate as appropriate.

◆ **Facilitation:**

A dedicated facilitator - the project manager, will preside over meetings. This facilitator will provide the guide and direct discussions in the meetings.

◆ **Documentation:**

Meeting minutes, including key decisions and action items, will be documented and shared within 24 hours.

◆ **Follow-up:**

Meeting action items will be tracked, with deadlines and responsible individuals identified.

The following table presents the communication matrix for this project, highlighting the stakeholders’ communication roles and responsibilities.

What	Objective	Who	Whom	When	How Often	How / Channel
Project Kick-off Meeting	Introduce project scope, goals, and stakeholders	Project Manager	All Stakeholders	Project Start	Once	In-person/Video Conference (Zoom)
Team Status Meetings	Review project progress, tasks, and issues	Project Manager	Project Teams	Regularly after kick-off	Weekly	In-person/Video Call (Microsoft Teams/Zoom)
Client Progress Updates	Update on project progress, milestones and performance	Project manager	Client and Sponsor	Regularly after kick-off	Bi-weekly	In-person, Email, Video Call (Microsoft Teams/Zoom)
Executive Updates	High-level summary of progress and key decisions	Project manager and Sponsor	Executive and Steering committee	Regularly after kick-off	Monthly	Email, Reports, Meetings
Quality Control Reports	Ensure quality standards are being met	Quality Manager	Project Team	As needed	As needed	Reports, Meetings Document Sharing (Google Drive)
Stakeholder Review Meetings	Review of deliverables and feedback	Construction Team, Quality Manager	Key Stakeholders, Clients	Regularly after kick-off	Monthly	In-person and Video Conference (Zoom)
Site Inspection Reports	Track construction quality and sustainability	Site Engineer/Quality Manager	Construction Team, Quality Manager	Regularly after kick-off	Weekly	Email/Shared Folder
Risk Management Updates	Identify and communicate project risks	Risk Manager	Project Team, Executive Sponsors	Regularly after kick-off	Bi-weekly	Email/Project Management Tool
Supplier/Contractor Updates	Coordinate materials delivery and tasks	Procurement Manager	Suppliers, Contractors	As needed	As needed	Email/Phone Calls
Final Project Review	Assess project completion, handover, and outcomes	Project Manager	All Stakeholders	End of project	Once	In-person/Video Conference

Table 19: Project Communication Matrix

Tables 20 and 21 present the project communication directory where the contact of all relevant stakeholders responsible for communication is recorded.

Name	Title	Email	Mobile	Channel
Laura Martínez	CEO	laura.martinez@ecobuild.com	+34 612 345 678	Email, Reports, video meeting
Carlos Gómez	Sponsor	carlos.gomez@ecobuild.com	+34 613 987 654	Email, In-person meeting, Reports
Ana Rodríguez	Project Manager	ana.rodriguez@ecobuild.com	+34 614 543 210	In-person meeting, reports, call, SMS
Miguel Sánchez	Sustainability Architect	miguel.sanchez@ecobuild.com	+34 615 876 543	In-person meeting, reports, call, SMS
María López	Quality manager	maria.lopez@ecobuild.com	+34 616 234 567	In-person meeting, reports, call, SMS
Sara Fernández	Civil Engineer	sara.fernandez@ecobuild.com	+34 618 876 432	In-person meeting, reports, call, SMS
David Morales	Renewable Energy Engineer and Consultant	david.morales@ecobuild.com	+34 619 345 210	In-person meeting, reports, call, SMS
Isabel García	Procurement Manager	isabel.garcia@ecobuild.com	+34 620 123 456	In-person meeting, reports, call, SMS
José Ortega	Construction Team	jose.ortega@ecobuild.com	+34 621 654 321	In-person meeting, reports, call
Natalia Ruiz	Legal Manager	natalia.ruiz@ecobuild.com	+34 622 345 678	In-person meeting, reports, call
William Alonso	Health and Safety Supervisor	william.alonso@ecobuild.com		In-person meeting, reports, call

Table 20: Project Stakeholder Register (internal)

Name	Title	Email	Mobile	Channel
Carmen Alonso	Clients	carmen.alonso@ecobuild.com	+34 622 941 810	In-person meeting, reports, call
Javier Hernández	Suppliers	javier.hernandez@ecobuild.com	+34 617 098 765	In-person meeting, reports, call
Pablo Castillo	Neighbor's and Local community	pablo.castillo@ecobuild.com	+34 623 987 654	In-person meeting, reports, call
Carmen Pérez	Local Council	carmen.perez@ecobuild.com	+34 624 543 210	In-person meeting, reports, call

Table 21: Project Stakeholder Register (external)

*All contact details are made-up and are used for this project alone.

5.3 Scope Definition

The project scope defines the objectives, deliverables, and boundaries of a project. It outlines what is included and excluded, ensuring clear expectations. This helps guide the project team and manage stakeholder expectations effectively.

5.3.1 Requirements

The success of the project relies on a well-defined scope that outlines clear requirements. This document details the program's goals, deliverables, and necessary resources. By outlining the needs of various stakeholders the scope ensures everyone involved has a shared understanding of the program's direction and how it will be achieved.

ID	Needs/objectives	Stakeholder	Description
Renewable Energy Integration	Reduce energy consumption by 50% compared to a conventional house by monthly monitoring energy consumption and compare it to traditional housing standards.	Renewable Energy Engineer	Incorporate solar panels, wind turbines and other renewable energy generation systems.
Thermal Insulation Integration	Reduce heat loss and gain by 40% using high-efficiency insulation materials.	Civil Engineer	Use high-efficiency materials for insulation of walls, ceilings, and floors.

Rainwater Harvesting and Water Recycling Integration	Reduce potable water consumption by 40% through rainwater harvesting and greywater recycling	Sustainability Architect	Implement systems to collect and store rainwater for irrigation and other non-potable purposes. Install systems for the treatment and reuse of greywater in the home.
Sustainable Building Materials	Use at least 70% of building materials that are recycled, recyclable, or have low environmental impact.	Procurement	Use recycled, recyclable, and low environmental impact materials. Ensure that the materials used have certifications that guarantee their sustainability.
Comfort and Well-Being	Maintain a comfortable indoor temperature (between 20-25°C) and improve indoor air quality and occupant well-being by 25%.	Project Manager	Ensure that housing design promotes comfort and ergonomics for inhabitants.
Regulatory Compliance	Obtain all necessary permits and certifications (LEED, BREEAM) within 3 months of project initiation.	Legal Officer	Ensure that the project complies with all local building and sustainability rules and regulations and obtain all necessary certifications and permits.
Suppliers Back Up	Establish contracts with 5 suppliers specialized in sustainable materials and technologies.	Procurement	Establish agreements and contracts with suppliers. Ensure deliveries and quality of materials.

	Make sure that we have a backup supplier for all the materials needed.		
Budget - time Planning and Management	The overall cost of the project is controlled 500.000,00 €. Complete the project within the 12 months.	Project Manager	Develop a detailed budget covering all aspects of the project, from materials procurement to labor and regulatory compliance costs. Monitor and adjust the budget as necessary to avoid cost overruns. Develop a timing schedule to make sure that we meet the project timings.

Table 22: Scope Requirements

5.3.2 Project Scope

This section concerns a detailed description of the included and excluded project activities

Included	Excluded
- Construction Management: Manage all activities related to the physical construction of the house this involves the foundations and main structure.	- Future Regulatory Changes: Compliance with new regulations introduced after the construction has finalized - Marketing and sales: The creation of marketing strategies, campaigns, and plans to promote the self-sustainable house. Direct sales efforts,

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Procurement Management: Establishing and managing contracts with suppliers of sustainable materials and technologies ensuring that all necessary materials and services are acquired efficiently and cost-effectively. - Regulatory Compliance: Obtaining all necessary permits and certifications, ensuring adherence to local sustainability laws and regulations. - Project Management: The initiation and planning phases will include the goals and objectives of the project. During that phases the management of stakeholders, resources, budget, time, communications, risks and quality will be defined. The execution of the project will include all the tasks will be group. - Design Management: Manage the development of initial sketches and concepts that align with the project’s goals in order to be submitted on time. - Closure and Handover: Measure the impact, effectiveness, and sustainability of the whole project. Prepare a report with all the analysis to be considered. 	<p>including lead generation, customer outreach, and closing sales deals. Designing and executing advertising campaigns, including digital marketing, print ads, and social media promotions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Land Acquisition: Identifying and selecting potential lands for the project. Engaging in negotiations with landowners to purchase or lease the land. - BIM Management: Developing or customizing BIM software tools specifically for the project. - Waste Management System in House: Developing new technologies or systems for waste management and recycling. Managing waste generated after the construction phase, such as during the occupancy and use of the house.
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Table 23: Project Scope

5.3.3 Product Scope

The product that we will offer to our customers is a self-sustainable house designed to provide a balance between modern comfort and environmental responsibility. The house will be equipped with advanced energy generation systems, including solar panels and wind turbines. The

water management will be optimized through rainwater harvesting and greywater recycling significantly reducing water waste. Constructed with sustainable materials the house will offer a good insulation and natural ventilation maintaining a comfortable indoor climate and good air quality.

Included	Excluded
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renewable Energy Systems: Installation of solar panels, wind turbines, energy storage and other renewable energy generation systems. - Water Management Systems: Installation of Rainwater harvesting systems, greywater recycling systems, and efficient plumbing fixtures. - Sustainable Building Materials: Use of recycled, recyclable, and low environmental impact materials with sustainability certifications. - Thermal Insulation, Cooling and Ventilation: High-performance insulation materials to provide thermal resistance. Natural ventilation that promote a good airflow. - Enhance Comfort and Well-Being: Ensure a good indoor temperature and high quality air that promote a wellbeing for the occupant. - Construction: Construction of the foundations and of the main structure of the building. This involves all parts of the house like: pipes, roof, floor, etc. - Design: Develop initial sketches and concepts that align with the project’s goals. Transform preliminary designs into detailed plans, including technical specifications, materials, and systems integration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-Sustainable Materials: Use of materials that do not meet sustainability criteria or lack certifications. - Luxury Features: High-end luxury features that do not contribute to sustainability or energy efficiency. - Structural Changes Post-Construction: Any alterations or additions to the structure after the construction phase. - Maintenance and Operations Post-Construction: Ongoing maintenance and operational costs after the project handover.

Table 24: Product Scope

5.3.4 Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

The project has been broken down into different tasks and activities that need to be accomplished in order for the project to be successful, as specified on the chart below:

Illustration 14: Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

5.3.5 WBS Dictionary

As standard, the project has many different activities that combined end up being the execution of each and every task. Its definition and detailed description has been developed below in different templates and briefly described. This is only a sampling of all the cards that each activity has.

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	1.1 & 1.2
Work package name	Initiation and Planning
Responsible organization	Project Manager
Work package description	Completion of all the Project Management Plans, where scope, budget, time tasks, strategies, risks, quality and several other aspects are defined.
Approve	CEO, Project Manager and Sponsor

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	2.2
Work package name	Certifications
Responsible organization	Legal Manager and Renewable Energy Consultant
Work package description	Develop a plan to match the systems and sustainable technologies with the green certifications (LEED, BREAM...) in order to get them with the best marks.
Approve	Project Manager

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	3.4
Work package name	Intern structure
Responsible organization	Civil Engineer, Sustainability Architecture and Renewable Energies Consultant
Work package description	Plans implementation for the inner part of the building, taking into account the sustainable and renewable sources demands.
Approve	Project manager

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	4.1
Work package name	Sustainable systems selection
Responsible organization	Sustainable Architecture, Renewable Energy Consultant and Procurement Manager
Work package description	Compare and analyze all the systems chosen in the designing stage and end up with the best selection regarding efficiency, sustainability and quality requirements specified.
Approve	Project manager

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	4.2
Work package name	Suppliers' selection
Responsible organization	Procurement Manager and Renewable Energies Consultant
Work package description	Search and choice of suppliers that can provide the demanded materials and quality standards needed, together with the best qualification in green certification and proximity (tender). Quality tests to be developed before formalizing the final contact.
Approve	Project manager

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	5.1
Work package name	Construction quality requirements
Responsible organization	Quality Manager and Construction Team
Work package description	Verification of all the sustainability and energy efficiency construction processes and construction plan development.
Approve	Project manager

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	6.4
Work package name	Installations
Responsible organization	Construction Team, Sustainability Architecture and Renewable Energy Consultant
Work package description	Integrate all the sustainable systems and the main building services (mechanical, electrical, plumbing and carpentry)
Approve	Project manager

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Dictionary	
Work package ID	7.1
Work package name	Closure of the project
Responsible organization	Project Manager
Work package description	Wrap up conclusions, feedback and stakeholders analysis
Approve	CEO and Project manager

Table 25: WBS Dictionary

5.4 Procurement Management Plan

This procurement management plan is essential for ensuring the timely supply of necessary materials for the construction of the self-sustainable house. It aims to facilitate smooth project implementation while adhering to both time and budget constraints. The planned purchases include eco-friendly building materials, expenses related to site preparation, fees for skilled labor, and costs associated with sustainable systems installation, such as solar panels and rainwater harvesting systems.

The procurement process will be overseen by the administration and finance department, which will work closely with the project team to ensure alignment on expectations and requirements.

The first step involves defining the overall procurement strategy. Next, items will be categorized by type, and the most effective approaches for acquiring each category will be determined. We will then establish the necessary contracts to guarantee quality throughout the entire procurement cycle without compromising project constraints.

The procurement process consists of several steps, each following clear guidelines to ensure efficiency. The key steps in our procurement process include:

1. Planning the necessary purchases.
2. Creating a detailed list of required items.
3. Identifying and evaluating potential suppliers and external workers.
4. Requesting quotes, comparing prices, and placing orders.
5. Signing and managing contracts.
6. Receiving materials and processing payments.

By following these steps, we aim to ensure a successful and sustainable construction process for the self-sustainable house.

5.4.1 Procurement Strategy

It is essential to create a roadmap that details how the materials and services needed for the self-sustainable house project will be sourced and acquired. The process will be visually represented in the following chart to provide a clearer overview of the procurement activities.

Procurement Phase	Description	Executor
1.Sustainable systems selection	The procurement office selects sustainability systems based on the project goals and certifications.	Project Manager procurement office based on sustainability engineer guidance
2.Suppliers Selection	The project manager and the procurement office evaluate proposals based on price, sustainability, and alignment with project goals. They select the best suppliers for sustainable materials and systems.	Procurement office and project manager
3.Materials selection	The project manager and the procurement office evaluate materials based on price, sustainability, and alignment with project goals. They select the best options to achieve the quality and standards defined for the project.	Procurement office and project manager
4.External contractors (services and workers)	The procurement office selects the required external contractors such as installators, plumbers, and other construction workers, maintains relationships with them, ensuring quality and delivery performance. They communicate regularly and monitor progress, informing the project manager.	Procurement office and project manager

Table 26: Procurement Strategy

5.4.2 Identification and Categorization

A procurement strategy is designed to enhance the steps outlined earlier, offering a clear roadmap for sourcing and acquiring the materials and services necessary for the construction of the self-sustainable house.

This strategy incorporates essential components and steps to ensure that procurement activities align with the project's goals and objectives.

A visual representation of this strategy is provided in the following chart:

Category	Package	Type of Contract	Cost (€)
Materials	Structure Foundation	Unit price contract	€ 52.750
	Building Construction	Unit price contract	€ 86.065
External Services	Supervision	Fixed price (FFP)	€ 9.648
	Constructors	Fixed price (FFP)	€ 5.760
	Electricians and Installers	Unit price contract	€ 5.760
	Plumbers	Fixed price (FFP)	€ 5.760
	Carpenters	Fixed price (FFP)	€ 2.786
	Painters	Fixed price (FFP)	€ 2.844
	Drywall panel installers	Fixed price (FFP)	€ 2.700

Table 27: Identification and Category of Procurement Strategy

Illustration 15: Cost Distribution

5.4.3 Purchase Documents

We analyzed each purchase package, focusing on its characteristics, requirements for suppliers, the necessary documentation, and the risks associated with the package. The objective is to ensure alignment between the purchasing strategy and the program's key goals.

Package Name		
Structure foundation materials		
Package Description		
Provide all the required materials for the foundations		
Supplier Requirements	Documentation	Associated Risks
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certification of material quality (e.g., ASTM standards) - Proven track record of supply reliability - ISO or similar quality certification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Material safety data sheets (MSDS) - Delivery schedules and invoices - Product specifications and test results - Warranty information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variability in material quality - Delivery delays impacting the schedule - Potential for cracking or structural failure - Non sufficient resistance

Package Name		
Building construction materials		
Package Description		
Provide all the required construction materials for building the house		
Supplier Requirements	Documentation	Associated Risks
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capacity to meet project timelines - Proven quality of materials - Variety in design options - Compliance with security and energy efficiency standards - Customization options available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product specifications and test results - Warranty information - Compliance documentation - Relevant certifications and licenses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leaks due to poor-quality materials - Non-compliance with building codes - Delays in delivery affecting project timelines

Package Name		
External Services		
Package Description		
Construction team (construction supervisor, constructors, electricians and installers, plumbers, carpenters, painters, drywall panel installers.		
Supplier Requirements	Documentation	Associated Risks
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience in this kind of projects - Knowledge in building techniques - Qualifications, degrees and certifications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service agreements and warranties - RFP - Contractual agreements - Non-disclosure agreements - Qualifications and Experience documents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poor workmanship leading to leaks or failures - Compliance issues - Scheduling conflicts impacting project timelines

Table 28: Purchase Package Documents

5.5 Quality Management Plan

This Quality Management Plan outlines the procedures and processes for ensuring that the Self-sustainable House project meets its defined scope and requirements regarding product quality standards and management. The plan establishes quality control and assurance to clarify roles and responsibilities for managing quality throughout the project. The purpose of the plan is to ensure that quality is planned by defining:

- ◆ How quality will be managed
- ◆ Quality control activities
- ◆ Quality assurance activities
- ◆ Acceptable quality standards

The quality management approach for the Self-Sustainable Building project will focus on the quality of both the product and the project. The project will meet its quality objectives by optimizing an integrated approach to defining quality standards, measurement and continuous improvement.

The product's quality aligns with the company's sustainable housing standards, focusing on meeting established quality criteria and client satisfaction. Process quality will emphasize the sequence of activities to ensure deliverables meet organizational standards, ensuring successful project delivery. The quality managers and the team will define and document all quality standards which will be included in the project plan. Quality metrics will be established, measured, and analyzed throughout the project to assess success, with reviews by the project sponsor.

4.5.1 Quality Control

Quality Control (QC) ensures that the deliverables meet specified quality criteria during the project lifecycle. It involves regular inspection, testing, and reviewing processes to identify defects or deviations and proffer mitigation. This quality control focuses on the project's objectives to establish quality actions, activities and deliverables that meet the requirements for building a self-sustainable house. The quality control will be monitored using quality checklists, statistical sampling and non-conformance reports. Tables 30 and 31 outline the project objectives, the corresponding quality control actions and expected deliverables. A more detailed quality control for individual deliverables is shown in the following tables.

SN	Objectives	Key actions, activities and improvement	Deliverables and procedure
1	Construct a house with an energy self-sufficiency of 50% and above	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop an integrated energy system that combines renewable energy generation with energy storage solutions and regularly review designs for optimal energy capture and storage - Source high-efficiency insulation, windows, and renewable energy systems and regularly verify materials meet energy efficiency standards and inspect installation - Perform simulations to forecast energy needs and renewable output and compare model outcomes with target efficiency, adjusting designs as needed before construction - Ensure correct installation of renewable systems, HVAC, and insulation and regularly inspect systems post-installation to verify adherence to energy efficiency guidelines. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation and configuration of solar panels, wind turbines or other renewable energy sources. - Installation of energy-efficient lighting systems, as well as thermal insulation. - At least 50% energy self-sufficiency
2	Construct a house with water self-sufficiency of 40% and above	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validate that rainwater harvesting and greywater recycling systems are designed to meet or exceed the 40% self-sufficiency goal and conduct simulations to assess the estimated water collection and usage rates - Ensure all pipes, tanks, filters, and pumps meet durability standards for long-term use and use eco-certified, high-quality materials for water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of design systems to collect and reuse rainwater. - Implementation of grey-water recycling system

		<p>collection and filtration to prevent contamination and system failure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct regular inspections during the installation of water systems to verify compliance with design specifications and check for leak-proof connections and proper integration of all components. - Test water collection and recycling systems for efficiency and adjust for optimal performance and monitor water flow, filtration quality, and recycling rates to ensure functionality matches the self-sufficiency target. 	
3	Construct a house using at least 70% of materials that are sustainable and recyclable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inspect the suppliers to ensure compliance with recyclable standards insisting on certifications and documentation of material sustainability - Research and list approved sustainable materials meeting environmental certifications - Track all purchased materials in a sustainability log, noting percentage composition and maintain records of material certifications to ensure compliance throughout the project - Inspect incoming materials to verify compliance with sustainability specifications and schedule regular audits to confirm that on-site materials meet the 70% sustainability goal - Develop guidelines to reuse or recycle excess materials by set up on-site recycling stations to ensure waste management aligns with project goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detailed architectural and engineering designs that prioritizes the use of sustainable materials
4	Construct a house with a comfortable indoor temperature between 20-25°C without excessive use of heating or cooling systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verify insulation materials meet thermal performance standards and ensure correct installation with no gaps or thermal bridging - Inspect and confirm building orientation, window placement, and shading device meet passive design elements - Verify use of thermal mass materials in walls/floors; ensure compliance with design specs for proper heat retention - Conduct regular maintenance and calibration, confirm settings meet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of detailed architectural and engineering designs that prioritizes passive construction techniques. - Installation of energy-efficient lighting systems, as well as thermal insulation.

		<p>indoor comfort criteria with minimal energy use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Install and test sensors in key areas review data to verify temperature stability within the 20-25°C range 	
5	Construct a house with a self-reliant liquid waste recycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verify that waste recycling design meets regulatory standards for safety, hygiene, and environmental impact - Use high-quality materials that meet ISO 14001 standard for environmental management and system - Test the recycling system for leaks, flow rates, and filtration efficiency. - Calibrate sensors and pumps to ensure they function as required to maintain water quality - Develop safety protocols for system operation to handling potential failures or blockages - Establish emergency protocols in case of contamination or system breakdowns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of sewage recycling system

Table 29: Product Objectives for Continuous Improvement

SN	Objectives	Key actions, activities and improvement	Deliverables and procedure
1	Execute the project with a budget of €500,000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Track expenses regularly, comparing actual costs to budgeted costs - Implement cost-control measures to prevent overspending - Regularly review budget reports with stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sufficiently detailed budget plan - Budget performance analysis
2	Deliver all deliverables on time and complete the project within 12 months	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare a detailed schedule with milestones - Conduct regular progress checks to stay on track - Adjust resources or activities promptly to avoid delays 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project plan document and timeline - Establish role and responsibilities for all stakeholders -
3	Maintain health and safety work site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enforce safety protocols and conduct regular safety audits - Monitor compliance with health and safety standards continuously 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain health and safety protocol on site

4	Reduce construction waste by 60% through recycling and reuse practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement recycling and reuse strategies for materials - Monitor and track waste generation and reduction efforts - Provide training on sustainable waste practices for the workforce. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meet sustainable requirement and practice - Minimize construction waste
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Table 30: Project Objectives for Continuous Improvement

Quality Requirement	Certificates	Objectives	Requirement Measurement Test	Acceptance Criteria	Test Frequency
Implementation of detailed architectural and engineering designs that prioritizes passive construction techniques.	LEED/BREEAM Certification	To ensure sustainable design meets certification standards	Review design documentation and materials list	Meets criteria for energy efficiency, material sourcing, and waste management	Initial design review; updated quarterly
	ISO 14001 (Environmental Mgt.)	To align with environmental management practices	Assess material specifications for compliance	All materials sourced must comply with ISO 14001 standards	At material selection, sourcing and delivery
	EU Eco-Label or Eco-Certification	To use eco-friendly, non-toxic, and renewable materials	Conduct toxicity and sustainability checks on materials	Must meet eco-label or equivalent standards for sustainable materials	At every material supply, before construction
	CE Marking	To conform to EU safety, health, and environmental requirements	Test durability and resistance based on EU standards	Materials must pass strength, fire resistance, and environmental tests	At every material supply, and installation

Table 31: Quality Control for Implementation of Architectural and Engineering Designs

Quality Requirement	Certificates	Objectives	Requirement Measurement Test	Acceptance Criteria	Test Frequency
Reduce construction waste by 60% through recycling and reuse practices	ISO 14001 (Environmental Management)	To reduce construction waste by 60%	Waste assessment by tracking quantity of materials reused/recycled and total waste generated	Achieve at least 60% reduction in waste sent to landfill	Weekly
	Local Waste Disposal Certification	To comply with local recycling regulations	Conduct waste segregation audits on-site	90% of waste materials sorted for recycling	Monthly, with weekly spot checks
	Material Recovery Certification	To maximize material recovery	Measure volume of materials diverted for on-site reuse	Minimum 40% of total materials reused on-site	Biweekly inventory review

Table 32: Quality Control for Construction Waste Reduction

Quality Requirement	Certificates	Objectives	Requirement Measurement Test	Acceptance Criteria	Test Frequency
Implementation of design systems to collect and reuse rainwater.	ISO 14001	Environmental management compliance	Water quality testing (pH, turbidity)	pH between 6.5-8.5, turbidity < 5 NTU	Monthly
	LEED Certification	To meet sustainable construction standards	Volume collection efficiency test	Minimum 80% rainwater collection efficiency	Quarterly
	Local Health Code	Safe for intended uses	Microbial testing (E. coli, coliforms)	Non-detectable levels of E. coli, coliforms	Bi-weekly
	ISO 9001	Quality management in project processes	Installation inspection and verification	All components installed as per design and manufacturer's specs	At installation
	ISO 24512	Water reuse system standards	Storage tank inspection	No visible damage, corrosion, or leaks	At installation and handover
	Company Sustainability Standards	To maximize rainwater usage in non-potable systems	Flow rate testing (pipe systems)	Achieve a consistent flow rate within 10% variance	Monthly
	Local Building Codes	To ensure structural safety for collection and storage	Structural load testing	Tank and gutter structures meet local building codes	At installation and annually

Table 33: Quality control for Rainwater Collection

Quality Requirement	Certificates	Objectives	Requirement Measurement Test	Acceptance Criteria	Test Frequency
Installation and configuration of solar panels	Installer Certification	To ensure installers are trained and certified	Verify installer credentials and certifications	All installers must have valid, up-to-date certification	Once before hiring
	Panel Quality Certification	To guarantee panel quality meets standards	Check certification documents and panel labelling	Panels must meet industry quality standards	Once before procurement
	System Efficiency Check	To ensure maximum energy output from panels	Measure system output under controlled conditions	Output must be within 95% of the manufacturer's stated efficiency	After installation and handover
	Voltage and Current Testing	To verify proper configuration and electrical performance	Test voltage and current output per panel	Voltage and current must align with system specifications	After installation and handover
	Structural Stability	To ensure secure and safe mounting	Inspect mounting hardware and installation	Panels must be securely mounted, withstand wind loads, and be level	During installation
	Electrical Continuity	To confirm no faults in wiring and connections	Perform continuity and insulation tests	Resistance must meet standards, with no breaks or shorts	After installation
	System Monitoring Setup	To verify that monitoring tools provide accurate data	Test real-time data on monitoring platform	Data aligns with physical measurements and readings	Once, post-installation

Table 34: Quality control for Installation of Solar Panels

Quality Requirement	Certificates	Objectives	Requirement Measurement Test	Acceptance Criteria	Test Frequency
Deliver all project deliverables within 12 months	Project Timeline Certification	To deliver all project deliverables on time	Compare actual progress with project timeline	Tasks completed by scheduled milestones without delays	Monthly
	Progress Reports	To track progress of each deliverable to ensure timely completion	Measure % completion of each deliverable	Each deliverable must be on track to meet the planned schedule	Weekly
	Resource Allocation Reports	To ensure resource availability and usage aligns with project timeline	Track usage of resources against planned levels	Resources utilized as planned, with no shortages causing delays	Monthly
	Budget Compliance Reports	To stay within project budget limits to avoid delays	Track expenditures against budget	Budget within 5% of planned costs	Monthly
	Risk Management Reports	To mitigate project schedule risks	Evaluate potential risks and action taken	All identified risks have mitigation strategies, no schedule impact	Bi-weekly

Table 35: Quality Control for Delivering All Project Deliverables on Time

4.5.2 Quality Assurance

This project's Quality Assurance (QA) focuses on establishing a proactive framework to ensure quality is built into the processes used to deliver the Self-Sustainable Building. The QA will emphasize the prevention of defects through proper planning, process design, and continuous improvement.

The quality manager and the project team will assess compliance at planned intervals throughout the project to ensure all processes and tasks are correctly implemented and executed. Quality assurance objectives relate to regulation compliance to ensure that quality processes and standards are integrated into the project and prevent design, materials, and sustainability issues.

Key performance metrics for the project include Energy Efficiency, construction and materials, environment and sustainability, waste efficiency and safety. The established project tolerances for these metrics are the organizational standards for sustainable building. Tables 37 and 38 provide the detailed quality assurance matrices for this project.

Quality Assurance for the Product

Quality Area	Quality Standard/Requirement	Indicator	Responsible	Verification Method	Timing/Phase
Energy Efficiency	Compliance with Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU)	Building Performance Energy Rating (EPC)	Sustainability Architect, Renewable Energy Engineer	Energy simulations, building performance modeling	Design Phase, Post-construction Audit
Renewable Energy Systems	Adherence to Renewable Energy Directive (2018/2001/EU)	Percentage of energy sourced from renewables	Renewable Energy Engineer	Solar PV system performance testing	Installation, Commissioning Phase
Construction Materials Quality	Compliance with Construction Products Regulation (305/2011)	Quality audit score and client feedback rating	Procurement Manager, Quality Manager	Material certification, CE Marking Verification	Procurement, Delivery, Installation
Sustainable Materials use	Certification according to ISO 14024 or LEED/BREEAM standards	Percentage of eco-certified materials used	Procurement Manager	Supplier audit, eco-label verification, material tests	Procurement Phase, Delivery
Water Efficiency	Compliance with European Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)	Reduction in water consumption (L/day)	Construction Team: plumbing expert	Greywater recycling system tests, water consumption audits	Construction, Commissioning Phase
Waste Management	Adherence to EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)	Percentage of waste recycled or reused on-site	Construction Team: waste expert	Waste disposal logs, recycling documentation	Construction, post-construction
Thermal Installations	Compliance with Reglamento de Instalaciones Térmicas en Edificios (RITE)	Thermal Comfort Score (temperature and humidity)	Construction Team: HVAC expert	Inspection of heating and cooling systems, performance tests	Installation, Commissioning Phase
Fire Safety	Compliance with European Fire Safety Standards (EN 13501-1) and Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE)	Number of fire drills and equipment inspections	Health and Safety Manager	Fire-resistant material testing, evacuation route verification	Design, Construction, Commissioning
Environmental Impact	Environmental assessments as per Spanish Environmental Impact Assessment Law (21/2013)	Number of environmental non-compliance incidents	Renewable Energy Engineer	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) reports, public consultation	Pre-construction, Design Phase
Land Use and Rehabilitation	Compliance with Ley de Suelo y Rehabilitación Urbana		Renewable Energy Engineer: urban planner	Land use approval, zoning compliance checks	Pre-construction, Planning Phase
Worker Health and Safety	Compliance with Occupational Health and Safety (Ley 31/1995)	Number of site incidents/injuries	Health and Safety Manager	Site inspections, safety audits, training records	Construction Phase, Weekly Inspections
Energy Certification	Compliance with Energy Efficiency in Buildings (RD 235/2013)	Energy rating	Renewable Energy Engineer	Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)	Construction, Commissioning
Indoor Air Quality	Certification per LEED/BREEAM and local regulations	Indoor air quality index (AQI)	Renewable Energy Engineer: HVAC expert	Air quality monitoring, ventilation system testing	Construction, Commissioning
Structural Safety	Compliance with Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE)	Structural stability	Civil Engineer	Structural integrity inspections, material tests	Design, Construction, Final Audit

Table 36: Quality Assurance Metrics for Product

Quality Assurance for the Project

Quality Area	Quality Standard/Requirement	Indicator	Responsible	Verification Method	Timing/Phase
Schedule	Project timeline aligns with approved project schedule	% of milestones achieved on time	Project Manager	Weekly schedule reviews, milestone tracking	Throughout project
	Compliance with critical path and buffer time	Number of delays impacting critical path	Project Manager	Schedule variance analysis	Monthly
Resources	Resource allocation follows resource management plan	Resource utilization rate (% of resources used as planned)	Resource Manager	Resource audits, utilization reports	Throughout project
	Adequate supply of sustainable construction materials	% of sustainable materials used	Procurement Manager	Inventory checks, delivery schedules	Procurement, Construction
Labor Resources	Compliance with worker availability and skill level	% of workforce with required certifications	Procurement Manager	Worker skill audits, attendance tracking	Pre-construction, Construction
Cost	Adherence to approved project budget	Cost variance (Actual vs. Budgeted %)	Project Manager	Cost reports, budget variance analysis	Monthly, Project Close
	Materials and services meet quality standards without exceeding cost	% of cost savings on sustainable materials	Procurement Manager	Supplier cost comparisons, contract reviews	Procurement, Construction
	Project phase completion aligns with budget allocations	Budget adherence per phase (% of planned vs. actual cost)	Project Manager	Phase-wise budget reconciliation	End of each project phase

Table 37: Quality Assurance Metrics for Project

Key Quality Assurance Tools

- ◆ **Process Flow Diagrams:** Map out construction and design workflows to ensure quality checkpoints are included at critical stages.
- ◆ **Audit Checklists:** Ensure that all project activities align with established quality procedures.
- ◆ **Benchmarking:** Compare project quality metrics against similar successful projects to ensure best practices are followed.

DAILY ACTIVITY FORM	[Name of activity Date]
Stakeholder name:	
Activity schedule:	
Start:	
End:	
Description of task	
<i>Describe the task you are doing on that day</i>	
Duration of the during the task:	
<i>Total hours worked</i>	
Number of resources involve	
<i>Total number workers</i>	
Additional observation(s):	
Any observation or defect etc.	

Table 38: Quality Assurance Form (Daily activity form)

Responsibility for Quality Management

To ensure quality throughout the Self-sustainable House project, specific roles and responsibilities are assigned to resources and stakeholders to implement the quality management processes. These roles ensure accountability at all stages of the project as shown in Table 39.

Primary Responsibility	Key Collaborators	Tasks and activities
Project Manager	Quality manager, Project teams and other stakeholders	Overall responsible for ensuring that the project meets the defined quality standards.
		Monitors the implementation of the quality management plan and ensures alignment with project goals and stakeholder expectations.
		Oversees the resolution of quality issues and ensures corrective actions are taken in a timely manner.
Quality Manager	Project manager, Sustainability Architect, Procurement manager, Civil Engineer, Construction teams, Suppliers	Directly responsible for managing both the Quality Control and Quality Assurance activities.
		Develops and maintains the quality management plan, ensuring that it is followed throughout the project.
		Coordinates with team members and contractors to ensure quality requirements are met and that corrective actions are implemented where necessary.
		Prepares quality reports, identifies areas for improvement, and recommends best practices for enhancing quality.
		Implement quality control checks during procurement to ensure materials meet specifications before they are used on-site
Civil Engineers	Construction Team, Quality Manager	Ensure on-site work adheres to the project's quality standards by performing regular checks and tests on construction processes and materials.

		Report any defects, non-conformance, or quality issues to the Quality Manager.
		Execute corrective actions based on feedback from the quality team.
Procurement Manager	Project manage, Sustainability Architect, Civil Engineer, Constriction teams, Suppliers	Identify and procure materials that comply with sustainability standards, such as those with low environmental impact, recycled content, or high energy efficiency ratings (e.g., certified by ISO 14024, LEED, or BREEAM).
		Ensure that materials like insulation, solar panels, and water systems align with the project’s energy efficiency and environmental objectives
		Evaluate and select suppliers based on their ability to provide sustainable, high-quality products that meet project specifications
		Assess supplier certifications (e.g., eco-labels, energy performance certificates) to verify compliance with relevant environmental and quality standards
		Negotiate contracts with suppliers that include clear quality standards, sustainability requirements, and penalties for non-compliance
		Conduct periodic audits of suppliers to ensure compliance with agreed-upon quality and sustainability criteria
		Ensure that sustainable, high-quality materials are procured within the project’s budget without compromising on quality or environmental standards
		Balance the need for cost efficiency with long-term quality and sustainability objectives
		Identify potential risks associated with material sourcing (e.g., delays, quality issues, or non-compliance with sustainability requirements) and develop mitigation strategies
		Resolve quality-related issues with suppliers, such as defective materials, ensuring that any problems are addressed quickly and effectively

Renewable Energy Engineer	Quality Manager, Project Manager, Civil Engineer	Responsible for ensuring that the project’s sustainability goals (e.g., energy efficiency, water management, and low environmental impact) are met.
		Conducts environmental and sustainability audits to verify compliance with relevant certifications.
Suppliers	Procurement manager, Civil Engineer, Quality Manager	Ensure that materials delivered meet the project’s quality and sustainability specifications
		Participate in quality audits to verify compliance with established standards.

Table 38: Key Quality Roles and Responsibilities

Escalation Process for Quality Issues

If any major quality issues arise, the following escalation procedure will be followed:

1. **Identification and Reporting**

The civil (site) engineers or construction team members will identify and report issues to the Quality Manager, immediately.

2. **Immediate Action**

The Quality Manager will assess the issue and recommend immediate corrective measures.

3. **Escalation to Project Manager**

The project manager will be informed if the issue poses a significant risk to the project’s timeline, budget, or quality outcomes.

4. **Stakeholder Involvement**

If required, the Project Manager will involve key stakeholders (e.g., clients, sponsors) to make informed decisions on handling critical quality issues.

5.6 Schedule Management Plan

5.6.1 Timeline

Apart from acknowledging the main tasks and processes the project needs to follow, it is also crucial to structure them in a proper timeline and make it fit on the different constraints following the deliverables. For that reason, we have developed the following schedule plan for the key activities of the project.

Illustration 15: MS Project Timeline

5.6.2 Critical Path

Not all the activities and processes can be overlapped and done at the same time, therefore, some of them become what we know as key tasks or activities. Combining all of them and their schedule, we can come up with the critical path, that will show the earliest the project can be completed taking into account the activities mentioned.

Illustration 16: MS Project Critical Path

No. Critical Path	Key Activities
1	Develop context analysis and project charter (WP 1)
2	Develop project plans (WP 1)
3	Identify relevant certifications for sustainable buildings (WP 2)
4	Prepare and submit applications for certifications (obtaining construction licenses and permits) (WP 2)
5	Research and evaluate potential suppliers (WP 4)
6	Manage suppliers' selection (WP 4)
7	Establish contracts and agreements (WP 4)
8	Ensure all the materials meet the sustainability standards and are sourced responsibly (WP 4)
9	Conduct suppliers' validation (WP 5)
10	Test all materials to be used in construction (WP 5)
11	Construction initiation (WP 6)
12	Manage building construction activities (WP 6)
13	Integrate sustainable systems (WP 6)
14	Monitor stakeholders progress and feedback
15	Closing, post evaluation and final report (WP 7)

Table 39: Critical Path

5.6.3 Milestone Plan

#	Milestone	Date	Deliverable	Responsible
1	Project Definition Finished	10.10.2024	Project Charter and Context Analysis	Project Manager
2	End of Initiation and Planning	12.11.2024	Project Plan	Project Manager
3	Kick Off Meeting	14.11.2024	Minute of the meeting, schedule confirmed	Project Manager
4	Obtaining Construction Licenses and Permits	24.01.2025	Plans for licenses, project report	Legal Manager
5	Design Completion	15.01.2025	Plans, reports, materials specifications, constructive details	Sustainability Architect + Civil Engineer + Lead Architect
6	Supplier Validation and Materials Testing Completed	21.03.2025	Contracts signed,	Procurement Manager + Quality Manager
7	Construction Initiation	24.03.2025	Report of Initiation	Architectural Supervisor + Construction Team
8	Foundations Completed	21.04.2025	Site status report	Architectural Supervisor + Construction Team
9	Building Construction Completed	24.07.2025	Site status report	Architectural Supervisor + Construction Team
10	Installation of the Sustainable Systems	07.08.2025	Site status report	Architectural Supervisor + Construction Team
11	Report with feedback of participants	15.08.2025	Final report	Sustainability Architect + Civil Engineer + Lead Architect
12	Project Closure	01.09.2025	Project closure and lessons learned report	Project Manager

Table 40: Milestone Plan

5.7. Transition and Handover

This transition plan is a formal document that outlines the process for handing over the completed self-sustainable building project from EcoBuild Solutions to the Client. The plan describes the approach to transitioning the project's operations and maintenance. The goal is to ensure a smooth transition of the building's operations, systems, and maintenance requirements.

The transition will include training, document transfer, testing, and ensuring all deliverables meet project specifications and sustainability standards. The Self-Sustainable Building project includes designing and constructing a residential building with utilities self-reliance. This project is currently with EcoBuild Solutions and will transition to the Client upon completion, not later than 12 months after the contract agreement. The project cost is €500,000.

Objectives of the Transition Plan

- ◆ Ensure a seamless transfer of operational control from EcoBuild Solutions to the Client
- ◆ Provide training for the proper use and maintenance of the building systems.
- ◆ Guarantee that all project deliverables meet the agreed-upon sustainability, energy efficiency, and quality standards.
- ◆ Transfer all relevant project documentation, certifications, and warranties to the client.
- ◆ Mitigate risks related to handover system malfunctions or maintenance issues.

5.7.1 Project Life Cycle

The Self-Sustainable Building project involves designing and constructing an eco-friendly and utilities self-reliant building. The project is scheduled to commence and end between 2nd September 2024 and 1st September 2025. The life cycle covers all project phases, including initiation, planning, execution monitoring and control and closure. The execution phase is central to the success of this project – designing and constructing a self-reliant building. Alongside monitoring, the most significant part of the project deliverables is completed at this stage, leading to the project closure upon meeting the requirements. The following image shows the life cycle of the project.

Illustration 17: Project Life Cycle

5.7.2 Milestone and Deliverables

Table 42 highlights the project's key milestones and corresponding deliverables. It also captures the teams responsible at each stage of the project.

Work Package	Milestone	Key Deliverables	Acceptance Criteria	Responsible	Accepted by
Initiation	Project Initiation	- Project Charter	Sign off by Project Manager	Project Manager,	Sponsor/CEO
Planning	Project Planning	- Project Plan - Context Analysis - Project schedule	Sign off by Project Manager	Project Manager,	Sponsor/CEO
Kick off	Kick off meetings	- Minute of the meeting	Sign off by Project Manager	Project Manager,	Sponsor/CEO
Execution	Design Completion	- Architectural design - Engineering designs - Sustainability reports - Materials specifications - Other constructive details	Sign off by Project Manager	Sustainable Architect, Civil Engineer, Renewable Energy Engineer	Sponsor/CEO
	Licenses and Permits	- Licenses and approval for construction - Compliance report for sustainability and planning code	Local council approval/Stamp	Project Manager, Legal Manager	Sponsor/CEO
	Foundation Completed	- Construction status report	Sign off by Civil Engineer	Construction Team	Project Manager

	Main Structure Completed	- Construction status and progress report	Sign off by Civil Engineer	Civil Engineer, Construction Team	Project Manager
	Installation of Sustainable Systems	- Construction status and progress report	Sign off by Civil Engineer	Civil Engineer, Construction Team	Project Manager
Monitoring	Report with feedback of participants	- Final reports on quality and compliance	Sign off by Renewable Energy Engineer	Project Manager, Civil Engineer, Construction Team	Project Manager
Closure	Transition and Closure	- Lesson learned reports - Closure reports - Project handover and acceptance	Sign off by Project Manager	Project Manager, Project Transition team, Client Team	Sponsor/CEO, Client

Table 41: Project Life Cycle and Deliverable Acceptance

5.7.3 Project Transition

EcoBuild Solutions will retain its existing staff on-site throughout the transition period for the Self-Sustainable Building project. Additional human resources are not anticipated to complete the project transition. This transition is expected to start 11 days before the final project closure. The company will inaugurate the transition team for this project shortly before the transition date to facilitate the necessary activities for a successful handover. EcoBuild Solutions expects the Client to have his team on-site at the commencement and to collaborate fully in the transition process. Also, the company will provide adequate workspace for both teams throughout the transition period.

Table 43 outlines the delivery activities and required documents for the project transition. This ensures that the product delivery and transition process is organized, transparent, and well-documented to meet the client and project standards.

Activity	Description	Required Documents	Responsible Party	Timeline
Final Inspection and Quality Check	Conduct a comprehensive review of the completed building to ensure it meets agreed project requirements and specifications	Final Quality Assurance Report	Quality Manager	1 week before delivery
Compliance Verification	Ensure all legal, safety, and environmental regulations are met	Building permit Fire safety certificate Health and safety certificate	Legal Manager/Civil Engineer	1 week before delivery
Sustainability Validation	Verify the implementation of sustainable systems and materials based on project requirements	Sustainability certification	Sustainability Architect/Renewable Energy Engineer	1 week before delivery
Customer Walkthrough	Organize a walkthrough with the client to demonstrate the features, systems, and functionalities.	Client walkthrough Checklist	Project Manager	3 days before delivery
Handover Document Preparation	Prepare a comprehensive handover package detailing the building's systems and maintenance.	Operations and Maintenance Manual	Project Manager	1 week before delivery
System Testing and Training	Conduct tests for renewable energy, water and waste recycling systems	System test reports Training Schedule	Civil Engineer/Sustainability Architect	3 days before delivery
Financial Reconciliation	Finalize project financials, including outstanding payments and cost variance analysis.	Final Invoice Payment Reconciliation Report	Procurement Manager	2 days before delivery
Legal Transfer and Documentation	Transfer ownership and legal responsibilities to the client.	Legal Transfer Documents Warranty Agreements	Legal Manager	On delivery day
Formal Handover Ceremony	Conduct a formal event to hand over the keys and documents to the client.	Keys Certificate of Completion Handover Checklist	Project Manager	Delivery day
Post-Delivery Support Agreement	Provide the client with contact details and support for post-delivery queries or maintenance.	Support Agreement Emergency Contact List	Customer Support Team	Delivery day

Table 42: Transition Activities and Documents Required

5.7.4 Transition Team and Responsibility

A transition committee will be constituted to manage the transition processes. This committee will consist of team members from EcoBuild Solutions and the Client. The roles and responsibilities of the committee members are outlined in Table 44.

Partner	Title	Responsibilities
EcoBuild Solutions	Project Manager	<p>Ensure all project deliverables are completed and meet sustainability goals</p> <p>Organize and oversee training and testing activities</p> <p>Provide support and documentation to the Client during the transition period.</p> <p>Coordinate the transition process and ensure all timelines are met</p> <p>Liaise between EcoBuild Solutions and the Client to address any concerns.</p> <p>Manage risks during the transition period, including any issues with system handovers or Client training</p>
	Quality Manager	<p>Ensure the project adheres to the quality control and assurance standards</p> <p>Provide quality documentation and final reports to the client.</p>
	Renewable Energy Engineer	<p>Ensure all sustainability features (solar power, rainwater harvesting, insulation, etc.) meet the performance metrics outlined in the project plan.</p>
	Civil Engineer	<p>Oversee the final testing and commissioning of mechanical and electrical systems to ensure they meet performance specifications.</p>
Client	Transition Team	<p>Assign team members to receive training on systems operation and maintenance</p> <p>Conduct a final inspection of the building with EcoBuild Solutions to confirm all deliverables</p> <p>Take over operational control of the building after successful handover.</p>

Table 43: Transition Committee Roles and Responsibilities

5.7.5 Property Transition

EcoBuild Solutions will retain all owned or rented physical and non-physical equipment after the project's completion and approval of the transition. This equipment includes the following:

- ◆ **Testing and Commissioning Equipment**

Electrical testers, insulation testers, or thermographic cameras used to validate energy and thermal efficiency.

- ◆ **Project Management Tools**

Any software or hardware, such as laptops, tablets, or proprietary project management software licenses, used by EcoBuild Solutions' team that aren't specific to the building's operation.

- ◆ **Specialized Tools and Diagnostics**

Renewable energy systems diagnostics tools and water treatment analysis tools. These items are needed for commissioning or inspection rather than ongoing operations.

- ◆ **Temporary Structures and Machinery**

Temporary infrastructure such as scaffolding, site offices, or heavy machinery used only during construction will be removed.

- ◆ **Intellectual Property (IP)**

Except where specified, intellectual property that directly results in the project deliverables will be transitioned to the Client to ensure the successful completion of the project. This includes transferring the ownership and licensing of project-specific IPs to ensure the client can operate and maintain the building independently while protecting EcoBuild Solutions' proprietary methods and technologies.

◆ **User Accounts and Passwords**

User account access and some level of authorization will be created by EcoBuild Solutions for the Client and his team for the transition period. This is to enable the Client and his transition team to access relevant information and reports related to the project and the transition. These access and authorizations will be disabled after the project’s formal handover.

5.7.6 Knowledge Transfer

There will be knowledge transfer from EcoBuild Solution to the Client within the transition period of this project. The purpose of this knowledge transfer exercise is to teach the Client practical operation of the facilities in the building to optimize utilization and benefits. This may take different forms depending on the Clients’ preference or what works best for both sides. The project manager will coordinate sessions for on-site physical operations of the building and class sessions. The sustainability Architect and the civil Engineer will conduct the on-site training for the Client. The Renewable Energy Engineer will conduct the class session to enlighten the Client on the necessary best practices for sustainable use of renewable resources. The schedule for the training is highlighted in Table 45.

System	Training Focus	Duration
Solar Power System	Operation, maintenance, and performance tracking.	1 day
Water Recycling System	Daily use, maintenance, and troubleshooting.	1 day
HVAC and Insulation	Efficiency tips and maintenance schedules.	1 day
Monitoring Systems	How to use building management systems to track energy and water usage.	1 day
Fire and Safety	Operation of fire safety systems, emergency protocols, and compliance checks.	1 day

Table 44: Training Sessions Schedule

5.7.7 Project Transition Schedule

Table 46 outlines the timeline for the project transition from EcoBuild Solutions to the Client. Any changes to this schedule will be subject to review and approval by both parties.

Phase	Activity	Responsibility	Duration
Pre-Handover	Final testing and commissioning of all systems.	Civil Engineer, Renewable Energy Engineer	3 days
Training	Conduct training sessions for the client’s staff on all systems (solar, water, HVAC).	Renewable Energy Engineer	6 days
Documentation Handover	Provide all relevant documentation to the client, including warranties, operation manuals, and performance certificates.	Project Manager	1 days
Final Inspection	Conduct a walkthrough with the client to inspect building performance and ensure all deliverables are met.	Project Manager, Client	1 days

Table 45: Project Transition Schedule

5.7.8 Handover and Acceptance Criteria

By implementing this transition plan, EcoBuild Solutions will ensure that the Client is equipped with practical knowledge to manage and maintain the self-sustainable building. Also, all relevant documents will be handed over to the Client. The Client will utilize an agreed transition checklist to determine that all activities associated with the transition have been completed. Upon satisfaction with all the tasks in the project transition, the Client will formally accept the project and both parties will sign the project handover documents (Table 5.7.5) to mark the completion of the project.

The success and acceptance criteria of the transition will be measured by the following:

- ◆ All systems are operational and meet the sustainability performance criteria outlined in the project plan.
- ◆ The Client and his team are fully trained and capable of operating and maintaining the building systems.
- ◆ All documentation has been handed over and verified by the client.

- ◆ The client has assumed full operational control of the building without any major issues during the first three months.

PROJECT HANDOVER INFORMATION	
Transfer Description	
Project Name: <i>Self-sustainable Building</i>	Project Number: #001 Date: 25/11/2024
Delivery Transfer:	
Transfer By: <i>EcoBuild Solutions</i>	Received By: <i>Client</i>
Transfer Content Checked: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Completed Self-sustainable house</i> - <i>Architectural and engineering designs</i> - <i>Building approval and permit</i> - <i>Relevant warranty and intellectual property</i> 	
Transfer Information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Completed Self-sustainable house with tested and functional systems</i> - <i>Architectural drawings, plans and engineering designs.</i> - <i>Original building approval and permit for construction</i> - <i>Information relating to warranties and contract agreements</i> - <i>Project-specific intellectual property rights to operate and maintain the property</i> 	
Observations: <i>No</i>	
Signature of Transferor: <i>EcoBuild Solutions</i>	Signature of Receiver: <i>Client</i>
Approval of Request: <i>Client</i>	Date: 25/11/2024

Table 46: Project Handover Information

5.8. Resource Management Plan

To guarantee that resources are efficiently allocated throughout the different stages of the self-sustainable house project, the following resource management processes must be established:

1. Resource Management Planning

Develop a strategy for how resources will be organized and utilized.

2. Estimating Resources for Activities

Identify the specific resources (materials, equipment, and labor) needed for each phase of the construction.

3. Acquisition of Resources

Secure the necessary materials, equipment, and skilled labor to meet project requirements.

4. Team Development and Management

Build and manage a skilled workforce, ensuring the right people are in place at each phase.

Resource Monitoring and Control

Track and manage resources throughout the project to ensure efficient use and prevent shortages or overuse.

This plan's objective is to detail the process for acquiring the right resources, including the necessary skill sets, along with the timeline for their involvement. It also outlines how team performance will be evaluated, and the systems for recognition and reward. All these elements are aimed at ensuring the successful completion of the project.

5.8.1 Resource breakdown structure (RBS)

The RBS serves as a detailed guide for all resources required to successfully complete the self-sustainable house project. It offers a hierarchical view, organizing resources by function and type, providing a clear and structured overview of what is needed for each phase of the project. This approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the project's resource requirements, from labor and materials to specialized equipment and sustainable technologies.

Illustration 18: Resource Breakdown Structure (RBS)

5.8.2 Organization Structure of the project (OBS)

The OBS reflects the specialized departments, ensuring every aspect of the self-sustainable house project is covered. Each department is responsible for its specific tasks, ensuring smooth operations, resource management, and compliance with the sustainability and financial goals of the project.

This OBS ensures that all team members and departments are aligned with the goals of delivering a high-quality, energy-efficient, self-sustainable house within the timeframe and the budget.

Illustration 19: Organization Structure of the project (OBS)

5.8.3 Roles

The following table describes the roles of resources for this project.

ROLES	PHASE	ACTIVITIES
CEO	Design	In charge of the overview and acceptance
	Execution	In charge of the overview and acceptance
	Final delivery and closure	In charge of the overview and acceptance
SPONSOR	Design	Supporting the project financially but also in terms of authority and strongly related with the high level stakeholders and key decisions.
	Execution	Supporting the project financially but also in terms of authority and strongly related with the high level stakeholders and key decisions.
	Final delivery and closure	Supporting the project financially but also in terms of authority and strongly related with the high level stakeholders and key decisions.
PROJECT MANAGER	Design	Responsible for the management of the plans and structure of all the project. Needs to coordinate and manage all the activities in order to reach the deadlines within the planned budget.
	Execution	Coordinate and manage all the activities in order to reach the deadlines within the planned budget. Take decisions, direct the team to achieve the goals defined for the project. Monitor the budget and schedule progress during the execution and identify required changes to communicate them to stakeholders.
	Final delivery and closure	Make sure the compliance criteria is achieved and participate in the handover process
SUSTAINABILITY ARCHITECT	Design	Responsible for the main design, following the distribution and comfort requirements, the renewable energy criteria, the sustainable aspects and regulations compliance.

	Execution	Responsible for the construction of the foundations and building, following the design criteria and taking decisions to ensure the project achieves the quality and requirements defined.
	Final delivery and closure	Responsible for the final delivery, making the corrections marked by the supervisor, and ensuring the project achieves the quality and requirements defined and the sustainable criteria compliance.
CIVIL ENGINEER	Design	Takes care of the structural calculation and delivery of all structural plans, define its materials, developing a durable and sustainable body for the house, that will be strongly bonded to the architect in order to find the best sustainable solutions.
	Execution	Oversees that the structural design is being strictly followed, without compromising the resistance of the elements and the final quality of the structure.
	Final delivery and closure	Certifies that the structural design was strictly followed, without compromising the resistance of the elements and the final quality of the structure in the handover of the project
RENEWABLE ENERGY ENGINEER	Design	Guidance and close work with the design team to ensure the most adequate renewable energy systems to achieve the goals defined for the project.
	Execution	Control during the execution of the best energetic systems for the house. In charge of all the supplies including water, electricity and climate. Needs to ensure the house can be run off-grid.
	Final delivery and closure	Certificate that all the renewable energy systems achieve the standards and regulation compliance defined for the project.
PROCUREMENT MANAGER	Design	Manage the main material suppliers as well as tech systems for the smart house and external resources. Plan all aspects in the procurement and election of suppliers and human resources

	Execution	Need to ensure the right time delivery for the resources with no delay or suppliers issues.
	Final delivery and closure	Manage the closure and compliance of the contracts with all external resources
CONSTRUCTION TEAM	Execution	Takes part in the entire construction process, coordinating between different teams and ensuring the project stays on schedule and within budget.
	Final delivery and startup of the water treatment systems	Reviews all changes required by the supervisor and the compliance of the quality requirements in each of the components of the house and foundations.
QUALITY MANAGER	Execution and Final delivery	Develop regular reports and analysis that ensure the construction meets the standards of sustainability and quality established on the plan.
LEGAL MANAGER	Design	Develop the strategical plan to accomplish with the current laws and requirements such as council licenses, construction licenses. Also in charge of the requirements coming from the certifications needed.
	Execution	Monitoring and control of the compliance of all aspects determined in the contracts and in all regulations.
	Final delivery and closure	Monitoring and control of the compliance of all aspects determined in the contracts and in all regulations.
Health and Safety Supervisor	Execution	Responsible for the well-being of each and every member or contractor involved in the construction. Ensures the correct procedures and supervises the environmental part as well.

Table 47: Resources Roles

In the next chart we will further analyze one of the most important resources, the sustainability architect.

ROLE	PHASE	RESPONSABILITIES	SKILLS	AUTHORITY	HOURS REQUIRED	COST
SUSTAINABILITY ARCHITECT	Design	Responsible for the main design, following the distribution and comfort requirements, the renewable energy criteria, the sustainable aspects and regulations compliance.	Creativity, innovation, expert architectural criteria			
	Execution	Responsible for the construction of the foundations and building, following the design criteria and taking decisions to ensure the project achieves the quality and requirements defined.	Decision making, leadership, solution oriented and proactivity.	Decision taking relevant for the project.	1.000 €	28.600€
	Final delivery and closure	Responsible for the final delivery, making the corrections marked by the supervisor, and ensuring the project achieves the quality and requirements defined and the sustainable criteria compliance.	Organizational skills, quality criteria, authority.			

Table 48: Sustainability Architect Role Analysis

5.8.4 Responsibilities Matrix (RACI)

The following chart outlines the distribution of responsibilities within the project, detailing who is responsible, accountable, consulted, and informed.

Task/Deliverable	CEO	Sponsors	Project Manager	Renewable Energy engineer	Sustainability architect	Civil Engineer	Legal manager	Quality manager	Procurement Manager	Suppliers	Supervisor	Construction team
Management and coordination	A	C	R	C	C	C	C	C	C	I	I	I
Compliance and legal requirements	C	C	R	R	R	A	A	R	R	I	I	I
Building design	I	C	A	R	R	R	I	I	I	I	I	I
Procurement	C	C	A	I	I	I	R	I	R	I	C	I
Quality control	I	C	C	I	I	I	I	A	I	R	I	I
Construction	I	I	C	R	R	R	C	C	C	I	A	R
Closing and handover	I	C	A	R	R	R	I	A	C	I	R	R
		R	Responsible									
		A	Accountable									
		C	Consulted									
		I	Informed									

Illustration 20: Responsibilities Matrix (RACI)

5.8.5 Resource Utilization Plan

We have strengthened the project's resource utilization plan by monitoring the time invested by each resource in activities and their cumulative contribution throughout the project.

The breakdown of time worked by each team member is depicted in the following table:

Illustration 21: Resource Utilization Plan Chart

5.9 Risk Management Plan

The risk management plan is essential for this specific project, particularly given the innovative and ambitious nature of constructing a self-sustainable house. This project involves significant financial outlays, complex technological integrations, and coordination with multiple suppliers and regulatory bodies. It is crucial to anticipate and mitigate potential financial risks that could impact its execution and success. This plan will ensure that financial risks, from budget overruns to funding instability and inflation impacts, are clearly identified and proactively managed.

By adopting a forward-thinking approach to financial risk management, the project can develop effective strategies to minimize financial disruptions and maximize the project's feasibility. Implementing a financial risk management plan will not only safeguard the project's financial health but also enable agile adaptation to economic fluctuations and potential financial challenges as they arise.

This project, while innovative, is assessed to be within a manageable risk level with respect to financial exposure. The overall financial risk score is calculated based on the potential impact and probability of key financial risks identified. This proactive financial scrutiny allows for a strategic approach that enhances the project's stability and success, keeping financial risks well within a controlled threshold. The top three high-probability and high-impact financial risks to this project are:

- ◆ **Budget Overruns:** Arising from unforeseen costs or scope changes.
- ◆ **Inflation Impact:** Affecting the cost of materials and labor.
- ◆ **Funding Instability:** Due to variations in investment or funding landscapes.

5.9.1 Description of the Risk

The following Risk Breakdown Structure (RBS) delineates the key categories and specifics of potential risks associated with the project. This structure is designed to systematically identify and address various types of risks —financial, logistical, operational, external, security, and legal—that could impact the project’s success. Each risk category will be detailed with its causes and potential mitigation strategies, ensuring a comprehensive approach to a risk management.

Illustration 22: Risk Breakdown Structure (RBS)

5.9.2 Qualitative Risk Analysis

The following table assesses the impact criteria and probability of occurrence for each identified risk. Each risk is briefly described, followed by the calculation of its Probability-Impact (P*I) score and the corresponding result.

Probability		Impact		Score
Likelihood	Percentage	Consequence	Cost	
Almost certain to occur	>70%	Catastrophic	> € 25,000	5
Likely to occur frequently	50% - 70%	Major	€ 25,000 - € 15,000	4
Possibly and likely to occur	30% - 50%	Medium	€ 15,000 - € 10,000	3
Unlikely to occur but could happen	15% - 30%	Minor	€ 10,000 - € 5,000	2
May occur but rare	<15%	Insignificant	< € 5,000	1

		Impact				
		Low Impact 1	Minor Impact 2	Moderate Impact 3	High Impact 4	Severe Impact 5
Likelihood	Highly Likely 5	Moderate 5	High 10	Extreme 15	Extreme 20	Extreme 25
	Likely 4	Moderate 4	High 8	High 12	Extreme 16	Extreme 20
	Neutral 3	Low 3	Moderate 6	High 9	High 12	Extreme 15
	Unlikely 2	Low 2	Moderate 4	Moderate 6	High 8	High 10
	Rare 1	Low 1	Low 2	Low 3	Moderate 4	Moderate 5

Key:
 1-3 = Low
 4-7 = Moderate
 8-13 = High
 14 < = Extreme

Illustration 23: Impact and Probability Criteria

ID	Category	Risk	Risk description	Probability	Impact	Score
1.1	Financial	Budget Overrun	Exceeding €500,000 budget	2	4	8
1.2	Financial	Labor Cost Increase	Higher costs due to scarcity of skilled labor	3	3	9
1.3	Financial	Funding Instability	Uncertainty in funding availability	2	4	8
2.1	Logistical	Supply Chain Delays	Delays in receiving materials	4	4	16
2.2	Logistical	Material Availability	Unavailability of key sustainable materials	4	4	16
3.1	Operational	Technological Integration	Issues with integrating new technologies	3	4	12
3.2	Operational	Labor Shortages	Lack of skilled labor in sustainable construction	3	3	9
4.1	External	Regulatory Changes	Changes in sustainability regulations affecting compliance	4	5	20
4.2	External	Environmental Impact	Unforeseen environmental impacts	3	4	12
5.1	Security	Vandalism or Theft	Potential for vandalism or theft on-site	3	3	9
5.2	Security	Data Security	Risks of data breaches or loss of sensitive information	3	3	9
6.1	Legal	Non-compliance Penalties	Penalties due to non-compliance with regulations	3	5	15
6.2	Legal	Contract Disputes	Disputes arising from contract terms with suppliers	3	4	12
7.1	Material	Quality Variability	Inconsistent quality of materials received	3	3	9
7.2	Material	Damage in Transit	Materials damaged during transportation	3	3	9
8.1	Technical	System Failures	Failures in renewable energy or water systems	5	4	20
8.2	Technical	Installation Errors	Errors in the installation of sustainable systems	3	4	12
9.1	Climate & Location	Weather Impact	Construction delays due to adverse weather	3	3	9
9.2	Climate & Location	Geographic Limitations	Site-specific limitations affecting design and installation	3	3	9
10.1	Stakeholder	Community Objections	Local community opposition to the project	2	3	6
10.2	Stakeholder	Misalignment with Investors	Differing expectations between investors and project goals	2	4	8

Table 49: Qualitative Risk Analysis

5.9.3 Response Plan

The following **Response Plan** provides actionable mitigation strategies for each identified risk at the project. These strategies aim to reduce the likelihood and/or impact of risks, ensuring project objectives are safeguarded. The adjusted Probability-Impact (P*I) scores after mitigation are included for tracking improvements.

ID	Category	Risk	Score	Causes	Mitigation Strategy	New Score
1.1	Financial	Budget Overrun	8	Unexpected expenses	Strict budget monitoring and cost controls	5
1.2	Financial	Labor Cost Increase	9	Scarcity of skilled labor	Engage early with contractors; set agreements for stable labor costs	6
1.3	Financial	Funding Instability	8	Uncertain funding sources	Secure funding agreements; keep investors updated	5
2.1	Logistical	Supply Chain Delays	16	Supplier delays	Pre-order materials; establish contracts with penalties for late deliveries	12
2.2	Logistical	Material Availability	16	Shortages of sustainable materials	Diversify suppliers; identify local alternatives	12
3.1	Operational	Technological Integration	12	Compatibility issues with systems	Test technologies in advance; provide adequate training	9
3.2	Operational	Labor Shortages	9	Lack of skilled workers	Offer training programs; source additional contractors if necessary	6
4.1	External	Regulatory Changes	20	Policy changes in sustainability regulations	Engage with regulatory consultants; ensure continuous compliance monitoring	15
4.2	External	Environmental Impact	12	Unforeseen environmental damage	Conduct environmental assessments; adapt project to minimize impact	9
5.1	Security	Vandalism or Theft	9	Site security issues	Employ security personnel; install surveillance systems	6
5.2	Security	Data Security	9	Cybersecurity threats	Implement cybersecurity measures; restrict access to sensitive information	6
6.1	Legal	Non-compliance Penalties	15	Failure to meet regulatory standards	Regularly review compliance requirements; maintain detailed documentation	10
6.2	Legal	Contract Disputes	12	Misunderstandings in contract terms	Clearly define contract terms; use legal counsel for complex agreements	9

7.1	Material	Quality Variability	9	Supplier inconsistencies	Perform quality checks on delivery; select certified suppliers	6
7.2	Material	Damage in Transit	9	Inadequate handling during transport	Use reliable transport services; ensure adequate packaging	6
8.1	Technical	System Failures	20	Equipment malfunctions	Perform testing and maintenance; have backup systems	15
8.2	Technical	Installation Errors	12	Lack of technical expertise	Hire experienced personnel; monitor critical installations	9
9.1	Climate & Location	Weather Impact	9	Unpredictable weather conditions	Schedule flexibility; prepare for weather-related delays	6
9.2	Climate & Location	Geographic Limitations	9	Limitations due to site conditions	Adjust design to account for site-specific conditions	6
10.1	Stakeholder	Community Objections	6	Concerns from local residents	Engage community; conduct informational meetings to address concerns	4
10.2	Stakeholder	Misalignment with Investors	8	Differing expectations	Regularly communicate progress; align project goals with investor expectations	5

Table 50: Response Plan

5.9.3 Quantitative Risk Analysis

The following table assesses a quantitative risk analysis that will provide a cost for each identified risk at the project and as a result we will have contingency.

ID	Category	Risk	Probability	Cost
1.1	Financial	Budget Overrun	15 %	€ 1,500
1.2	Financial	Labor Cost Increase	30 %	€ 2,000
1.3	Financial	Funding Instability	15 %	€ 1,000
2.1	Logistical	Supply Chain Delays	50 %	€ 4000
2.2	Logistical	Material Availability	50 %	€ 3,000
3.1	Operational	Technological Integration	30 %	€ 2,000
3.2	Operational	Labor Shortages	40 %	€ 2,500
4.1	External	Regulatory Changes	50 %	€ 5,000
4.2	External	Environmental Impact	35 %	€ 2,500
5.1	Security	Vandalism or Theft	25 %	€ 1,500
5.2	Security	Data Security	30 %	€ 2,000
6.1	Legal	Non-compliance Penalties	35 %	€ 3,000
6.2	Legal	Contract Disputes	30 %	€ 2,500
7.1	Material	Quality Variability	25 %	€ 1,000
7.2	Material	Damage in Transit	30 %	€ 1,500
8.1	Technical	System Failures	60 %	€ 4,000

8.2	Technical	Installation Errors	30 %	€ 2,000
9.1	Climate & Location	Weather Impact	30 %	€ 2,000
9.2	Climate & Location	Geographic Limitations	25 %	€ 1,000
10.1	Stakeholder	Community Objections	15 %	€ 2,000
10.2	Stakeholder	Misalignment with Investors	10 %	€ 1,000
CONTINGENCY MARGIN				€ 47,000

Table 51: Quantitative Risk Analysis

5.9.4 Risk Sheet

Risk sheet					
Risk ID	2.2	Risk Name	Material Availability		
Probability	4	Impact	4	Score	16
Risk Description	Unavailability of key sustainable materials				
Causes	Shortages of sustainable materials				
Mitigation Action	Diversify suppliers; identify local alternatives				

Risk sheet					
Risk ID	9.2	Risk Name	Geographic Limitations		
Probability	3	Impact	3	Score	9
Risk Description	Site-specific limitations affecting design and installation				
Causes	Limitations due to site conditions				
Mitigation Action	Adjust design to account for site-specific conditions				

Table 52: Risk Sheet

5.10 Cost Management Plan

The cost plan serves as a breakdown of the necessary expenses to execute the project, from its initiation to its closure. In this plan we will make a decomposition of the expenditures to cover the project budget of 500.000 €.

5.10.1 Project Budget

The project budget was calculated taking into consideration the following expenses outlined in section 4.4.2.: human resources expenses and material expenses. In case of risky events we are considering a contingency reserve of 11% based on the quantitative risk analysis conducted in Section 4.9.4. A 6% management margin is integrated into the cost baseline to establish the final budget. The 6% was established considering that the project follows the company's usual way of working so there are not unknown's unknowns. Detailed breakdowns of human resources expenditures and other material expenses will be provided in the following section.

PROJECT BUDGET 500.000€	
Cost Baseline 470.000€	Management Margin 30.000€
Project Cost 423.000€	Contingency Reserve 47.000€
Materials 138.815€	Human Resources 283.185€

5.10.2 Cost Analysis

Human resources

The labor cost was determined by calculating the total working hours dedicated to the project for each internal and external resource, considering an hourly salary rate.

Resource	Hour Salary	Hours	Total (€)
CEO	40 €	100	4.000 €
Sponsor	31 €	150	4.710 €
Project Manager	28 €	2080	58.240 €
Sustainability Architect	29 €	1000	28.600 €
Quality manager	28 €	1000	28.100 €

Civil Engineer	28 €	800	22.000 €
Renewable Energy Engineer	28 €	1000	28.400 €
Procurement Manager	30 €	800	23.600 €
Construction Team	13 €	357	35.258 €
Construction Supervisor (external)	20 €	480	9.648 €
Constructors (internal)	12 €	480	5.760 €
Electricians and installers (external)	12 €	480	5.760 €
Plumbers (external)	12 €	480	5.760 €
Carpenters (external)	12 €	240	2.786 €
Painters (external)	12 €	240	2.844 €
Drywall panel installers (external)	11 €	240	2.700 €
Legal Manager	32 €	800	25.720 €
Health and Safety Supervisor	31 €	800	24.557 €
Total			283.185 €

Table 53: Human Resources Cost Analysis

In the case of the construction team we need to consider that this is the group of internal and external members that will be working directly on the construction of the building. This team includes different roles with different salaries, that is why it is differentiated in the above table.

Material Resources

The material cost was determined by considering all the materials that will be used and needed in order to build the self-sustainable house.

Package	Type of material	Contract Amount (€)	Percentage
Materials	Foundation Materials	52.750	38%
Materials	Construction Materials	86.065	62%
TOTAL		138.815	100%

Table 54: Material Resources Cost Analysis

Finally, as an overall of material expenditures, it is shown the distribution in the figure below, where is construction materials cost and foundations costs are the most significant costs, followed by sustainable systems and installation materials.

Illustration 24: Materials Cost Distribution Pie Chart

5.10.3 Treasury and Financing Plan

The project relies on economic support from the company, CEO and Sponsor, which have already provided the financial support for the project development. These stakeholders will require reports of the expenditure allocation. Finally, we will show a “S” curve that not only shows the costs and the accumulated value, but also the allocation in time. So, it gives an idea of when is necessary to have the money available during the timeline.

Illustration 25: Monthly Money Tracker "S" Curve

6. Project Control

Due to the complexity and duration of the project, there is always the possibility of changes and mishaps arising in any of the multiple stages. That's why a planned and structured change control system might facilitate the adaptation to those issues that can occur. It is widely known that any change will most likely affect the three key aspects of the project (scope, time and cost) and needs to be managed precisely to make the less impact possible on the whole project.

6.1 The Change Control System

This Change Management Plan's objective is to offer a methodical and clear approach to managing project modifications. Any project will inevitably undergo changes, but with the right management, these can produce better results and increase alignment with the project's objectives. This strategy tries to minimize risks and keep the project roadmap by making sure that all changes are carefully considered, authorized, communicated, and documented.

6.1.1 Change Control Flow

A lot of resources and effort is put in this project, also making a big impact for the local community in terms of sustainability and environmental efficiency, but the slightest issue can bring down the whole process. In order to avoid or mitigate those changes, we have thoroughly developed a strong change plan to follow the main steps and instructions in a general procedure, which we explain below:

- ◆ **Submission of the change request form:** both external and internal interested parties can bring up a change, having previously filled out the change request form.
- ◆ **Change request form review:** the submitted form has to be assessed regarding the risks, scope objectives, time and cost by the PM.
- ◆ **Change Control Board (CCB) evaluation:** once the PM has overviewed and evaluated the change, the main change control board must meet and appraise it.

◆ **Decision and implementation plan:** after the board's meeting, their choice needs to be communicated to the interested parties and stakeholders involved. Mainly, three possible scenarios can come out from the CCB's decision:

- Acceptance: approval is given to go ahead with the change
- Rejection: the change request does not comply with the criteria and the motives are explained to the parties and stakeholders
- Stand by process: the committee needs further information and calls in the parties and stakeholders

◆ **Change implementation plan:** the PM designs the plan to implement the requested change

◆ **Execution:** development of the tasks needed and mentioned in the implementation plan.

◆ **Change monitoring:** restructure and overview of the execution and the impact on the rest of the project activities involved. It can either be a positive or negative impact for the rest of the project.

◆ **Change closure:** document all the changes and updates that may arise from the change

Apart from the regular channel to request changes, there is also two other scenarios where the procedures change in order to optimize the available resources:

◆ **Critical change:** if a key participant or stakeholder raises up a change that can mean a big impact on the project (previously assessed by the PM), the CCB will automatically meet and decide which actions need to be taken from there onwards.

◆ **Minor change:** for a straightforward change (also previously assessed by the PM) the actuation of the CCB won't be strictly necessary and the change will be properly communicated. The implementation plan will also be registered but the change request form submission won't be mandatory.

The change control structure and procedure will be available for all the stakeholders and external and internal parties, following the next steps:

Illustration 26: Change Control Structure

6.1.2 Change Control Committee

A Change Control Board (CCB) will be established to guarantee precise change initiation, advancement, and closure. This committee uses systematic progression and the EcoBuild Solutions principles to supervise and manage change. The CCB oversees the reduction of possible risks, increases project benefits, and makes sure that changes are occurring in a planned and orderly manner. The members of the CCB are:

Position	Committee Role	Responsibility
CEO	Chair	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Supervises and approves the changes that involve the scope, time and budget of the project ◆ Has a global perspective from the structure and organization in terms of changes, what can provide a general and open-viewed strategy towards them.
Project Manager (PM)	Co-Chair	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Manage, assess and coordinate the change requests ◆ Applying defined criteria, filters the changes requested depending on the urgency and impact on the project ◆ Evaluates the changes regarding scope, budget and time impact and takes the decision to call in the CCB ◆ Documents and revises all the changes and updates on the project
Civil Engineer	Member	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Has a global view of most of the stages where changes can cause a big impact and can bring up solutions and methods to fix them.
Key parties and stakeholders	Submitters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Submit the change request form considering the procedure ◆ Add and provide information about the change and meet with the CCB if necessary ◆ Acquire or have the knowledge about the change requested in order to ask possible questions

Table 55: Change Control Committee Members

Regarding the decision, the CCB needs to make if changes arise, there needs to be a majority of the board in favor or against the change. The process will be effective and democratic, in which the results will be collected with the following forms:

Change Control Board - Decision				
Decision	Approved	Approved with conditions	Rejected	More info
Decision Date	[dd/mm/yy]			
Decision Explanation	[Main reasons and explanations from the CCB]			
Conditions	[Conditions to develop the change]			
Approval Signature	[Responsible]	Date Signed	[dd/mm/yy]	

Table 56: Change Control Board - Decision Sheet

6.1.3 Change Control Sheet

Change Control Sheet	
Application initiation Dep	Change of event manager
Application Date:	
Change Project:	Program Implementation Date:
Change Category:	
Description of changes	Before the change:
	After change:
	Reason for change:
Change of program:	
Risk Analysis and Expected Impacts:	
Change risk assessment	Evaluation department:
	Evaluation Content
Change review opinion	
Change reviewer's signature and date	

Table 57: Change Control Sheet

6.2 Change Management Case

Incident

The delivery of solar panels is delayed by one month due to supplier supply chain disruptions. This delay threatens to extend the entire project timeline and increase costs.

Summary of the incident
<p>Problem identification:</p> <p>Isabel Garcia who represents the procurement area has been informed about a delay of one month in the delivery of the solar panels.</p> <p>Isabel has been working on bringing a solution with the project manager in order to inform the project team and stakeholders about the delay and its implications. The first option considered by Isabel is to talk with the installation technicians of solar panels in order to check if they can reduce the installation time of the solar panels. In</p>

case there is no option to reduce installation timings Isabel will identify and negotiate with alternative suppliers to accelerate the delivery of solar panels and meet initial timings.

Considering this, he presents the following alternatives

Solution alternatives:

Alternative 1: Maintain the current solar panel supplier despite the delays in delivery, which will result in a delay in the deliverable of entire project.

Alternative 2: Reduce the installation time of the solar panels. This will result in an extra cost to be paid to the installer technicians since they will need to make extra hours in order to maintain the project timings.

Alternative 3: Identify a different solar panel supplier in order to accelerate the delivery. This will lead the project to increase its expenditures and change the original supplier selected.

Impact of each alternative

Alternative 1: Impact on time. Delay of one month in the deliverable of the project.

Alternative 2: Impact on costs. Considering the delay from the current supplier, 125 extra hours will be done by the solar panel installers which presents an extra cost of 1.500€.

Alternative 3: The alternative supplier present a cost per solar panel of 350€ compared to the 200€ of the initial supplier and a 18€ rate per hour for solar panel installation technicians compared to the 12€ of the initial supplier.

Areas of focus and risk.

2.2 Material Availability: Considering the risk analysis (section 5.9.4) there is a contingency reserve for this risk of 3000 EUR

Decisions taken:

After analyzing the alternatives, the most convenient option is alternative 2 since the cost impact is the lowest and we will keep initial timing of the project. Another positive point is that we will keep the initial supplier considered.

Re-planning the project:

The project plan has been revised to incorporate the changes in line with Alternative 2. Special attention was given to the triple constraints (scope, time, and cost) in the project plan. The Gantt chart and budget have been updated to reflect the 125 extra hours done by the solar panel installation team and the extra costs of 1.500€. This

adjustment aims to eliminate the impact of the delay on the project schedule while ensuring the delivery of the house. Considering that the cost impact of this change is considered minor the simple process change management flow was chosen to follow.

Table 58: Change Management Case

Approval of the change

Before the change was approved, the RFC formulary was filled out to introduce the change in the project and to start the request and announce the change. According to the change management flow, this sheet is sent by email from the procurement manager to the project manager.

Change Control Sheet	
Project name: Eco-Housing	Change request number: 1505 Date: 20.06.2025
Description of change request: Reduce the installation time of the solar panels. This will result in an extra cost 1.500€ and 125 extra hours done by the solar panel installation technicians.	
Submitted by: Procurement	
Current Status: Approved	
Affected project areas: Budget: Increase in 1.500€ (absorbed by the Contingency Reserve). Schedule: Increase in 125 hours, that will not affect the project timing since it will be extra-hours. Resources	
Observations: None	
To be implemented: 25.07.2025 – 07.08.2025	Overall risk result: 2.2 Material Availability
Decision result: Approved	
Approval of request: Project Manager: Ana Rodriguez	Date: 21.06.2025

Table 59: Change Control Sheet

Considering the simple process change management flow, once the change management is requested by the Procurement Manager, only the project manager has the responsibility of approving this change and consequently documenting the Change request.

Change Control Board - Decision				
Decision	Approved	Approved with conditions	Rejected	More info
Decision Date	21.06.2025			
Decision Explanation	According to the external circumstances is the best option to preserve the timeline of the project			
Conditions	N/A			
Approval Signature	AR	Date Signed	21.06.2025	

Table 60: Change Control Board - Decision Request

Even if this change is minor, the Historical Change Control Sheet is updated to reflect the facts.

Change Request Number	Description	Status	Implementation date	Comments
1505	Reduce the installation time of the solar panels	Approved	25.07.2025 – 07.08.2025	None

Table 61: Change Request Number

Given the fact that there is a minor change and the impact on the project is not significant, the Change Plan will be as simple as documenting the new agreement with the installation technicians. A further follow-up before the initiation of the installation of the solar panels will be planned to ensure compliance with the agreement. After the installation is done the change will be closed, and if any document updates are needed, they will be submitted within the change folder.

7. Closure

7.1 Criteria for Validation and Acceptance of Results

This project involves designing and constructing a self-sustainable house. The project's success is measured by delivering the completed house with the defined self-sufficiency in energy, water, and liquid waste management systems. The project success criteria will also be related to EcoBuild Solution's strategic goals, objectives, scope, and financial indicators. Overall, the success of this project adds to the company's experience and lessons learned on eco-friendly construction and sustainable development. Table 63 outlines the content of the project acceptance criteria.

Alignment with the company's strategic vision

EcoBuild Solutions' strategic vision involves active participation and leadership in the dynamic eco-friendly construction ecosystem. The self-sustainable building project aligns seamlessly with the company's vision by embodying commitment to adapting to industry needs, particularly the growing demand for environmentally responsible construction. Through this project, we deliver a high-quality, eco-friendly building that not only meets but anticipates the evolving standards in sustainable development. By integrating innovative technologies and sustainable materials, we reinforce our dedication to quality and position ourselves at the forefront of the construction industry's shift towards greener practices.

Validation of Goals and objectives

The project goal and objectives align well with the company's vision of delivering high-quality construction, expanding sustainable initiatives, and fostering innovation in construction practices. The project's validity holds when the goal and objectives are met and align with the company's strategic vision.

The project's primary validation goal is designing and constructing a self-sustainable house using advanced technology for utility self-sufficiency. This goal is validated through its alignment with the company's commitment to being a leader in sustainable construction by incorporating cutting-edge systems to manage energy, water, and waste autonomously, reflecting innovation and quality. The commitment to addressing potential internal and external regulatory, legal, and maintenance challenges shows a

proactive approach, ensuring the project’s viability and compliance with industry standards.

Project objectives are validated when the project is completed within the 12-month schedule, with a budget of €500,000 and meeting the sustainability quality requirements. These emphasize the company’s commitment to efficient project management, on-time delivery, and dedication to meeting client expectations.

Product objectives are validated when the project delivers the completed house with functional systems for self-sufficiency in energy (50%), water (60%) and waste management constructed using at least 70% sustainable or recycled materials.

Overall, the project goal and objectives fully support the company's medium- and long-term objectives of innovation, sustainability, and environmental impact reduction. This project meets client expectations and positions the company as a leader in innovation, sustainability, and environmental impact reduction. This project not only meets client expectations but also positions the company as a leader in self-sustainable construction, supporting both the company's vision and the evolving needs of the industry.

PROJECT ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA	
Project name: <i>Self-sustainable Building Project</i>	
Project manager name:	
Alignment with the company’s strategy	
Company’s strategy	Achieve(Y/N)
1. Does the project align with the company’s focus on delivering high-quality construction solutions?	Y
2. Does the project align with the eco-friendly and sustainable construction drive of the company?	Y
3. Does the project align with the innovation drive of the company?	Y
4. Does the project meet the company’s customer satisfaction drive?	Y
Validation of the objectives	
Objective	Achieve(Y/N)
1. Was the project completed within 12 months?	Y
2. Was the final actual project cost within €500,000 range?	Y
3. Did the project meet the self-sustainability requirement?	Y

4. Did the project meet the 50% energy self-sufficiency requirement?	Y
5. Did the project meet the 60% water self-sufficiency requirement?	Y
6. Did the project meet the liquid waste self-sufficiency requirement?	Y
6. Did the project meet the 70 % renewable material use requirement?	Y

Table 62: Project Acceptance Criteria

Scope Validation

The project is considered successful when all the deliverables are met. Scope validation is used to confirm work packages, tasks and deliverables, and directly contribute to meeting the project’s goal, objectives and requirements. Table 64 outlines the validation of the Self-Sustainable Building project, confirming that all aspects, from design to construction are met, and align with the company’s commitment to sustainability, client expectations, and regulatory standards.

Work package	Acceptance point	Achieved (y/n)	Validation	Date
Project Initiation	Project Manager at initiation completion		Sponsor/CEO	10.10.2024
Project Planning	Project Manager at planning completion		Sponsor/CEO	12.11.2024
Kick off meetings	Project Manager at start of execution		Sponsor/CEO	14.11.2024
Design Completion	Sustainable Architect at execution		Sponsor/CEO	15.01.2025
Licenses and Permits	Legal Manager at execution		Sponsor/CEO	24.01.2025
Supplier Validation and Materials Testing	Quality Manager, Procurement Manager at execution		Legal Manager	21.03.2025
Foundation	Civil Engineer at execution		Project Manager	21.04.2025
Main Structure	Civil Engineer at execution		Project Manager	24.07.2025

Installation of Sustainable Systems	Civil Engineer at execution		Project Manager	07.08.2025
Report with feedback of participants	Project Manager at control and monitoring		Project Manager	15.08.2025
Transition and Closure	Project Manager at closure		Sponsor/CEO, Client	01.09.2025

Table 63: Scope Validation

Lessons Learned

Lessons Learned for this project provide valuable insights for improving future projects in eco-friendly projects. The lesson-learned document will collect information that typically covers successes, failures, challenges, and opportunities for improvement. This helps the project team, and the company refine processes, mitigate risks, and enhance overall efficiency. Table 65 outlines the relevant information required for the lesson learned log

Lessons Learned Log				
Project Name: Self-sustainable Building Project				
Category	Issue name	Issue description	Impact	Recommendation
Date: Signature: Project manager:		Date: Signature: Name of submitter:		

Table 64: Lessons Learned

Financial Indicators

Financial indicators are essential metrics that help track the project's financial performance. In the Self-Sustainable Building project, these indicators will be used to evaluate the budget management and efficiency. The key interest is determining the degree to which indicators and the overall project's budget were adhered to. The initial budget estimates are compared to the actual expenditures. The project's financial indicators are shown in Table 66.

Financial Indicators Log			
Indicator	Estimate	Actual	Remarks/% deviation
CEO	4.000 €		
Sponsor	4.710 €		
Project Manager	58.240 €		
Sustainability Architect	28.600 €		
Quality Manager	28.100 €		
Civil Engineer	22.000 €		
Renewable Energy Engineer	28.400 €		
Procurement Manager	23.600 €		
Construction Team	35.258 €		
Construction Supervisor (external)	9.648 €		
Constructors (internal)	5.760 €		
Electricians and installers (external)	5.760 €		
Plumbers (external)	5.760 €		
Carpenters (external)	2.786 €		
Painters (external)	2.844 €		
Drywall panel installers (external)	2.700 €		
Legal Manager	25.720 €		
Health and Safety Supervisor	24.557 €		
Foundation Materials	52.750		
Construction Materials	86.065		

Table 65: Financial Indicators

7.2 Closure of Suppliers

Supplier closure is an important process in the closing phase of the Self-Sustainable Building project. It heralds the formal ending of existing suppliers' engagement in the project. One of the main objectives of supplier closure is to ensure seamless project completion through effective supplier management. The process involves signing a formal agreement and confirming contract closure from suppliers. This step ensures that all deliverables, contractual obligations, and financial commitments are met and documented.

Having maintained an effective communication channel, the suppliers will be regularly updated on the project's progress and changes relevant to suppliers. The communication will consider different suppliers' communication preferences and methods. This ensures that all suppliers know their roles in closing the supplier

relationship, including when to expect or present the final report, terminate contracts and settlements of outstanding invoices, if any.

Plan for Closure of Suppliers

It is crucial to properly plan the closure of engagement with suppliers for the project. This ensures a seamless transition to project completion by effectively managing the relationships with the suppliers. This will allow all parties to secure formal agreement and affirmation of project closure and settle all pending issues. For this project, the suppliers’ closure will be done through a formal meeting and distribution of final reports.

Closure Meeting with Suppliers

The closing meeting will bring together the project manager, procurement manager, quality manager, and key suppliers. This will provide an opportunity to acknowledge suppliers’ contributions to the project, discuss outstanding matters, and share experiences and lessons learned. In the formal meeting, the agenda will cover suppliers’ performance review, final deliverables and documentation. Also, financial and contractual review and feedback and opportunities for future collaborations will be discussed. Similarly, formal documents will be presented by the project manager confirming that the project objectives have been achieved (or not) and to close the project.

Distribution of the Final Report

After the closing meeting, the final report will be distributed to each supplier and relevant stakeholders. This report will summarize key points discussed, and resolutions attained at the meeting. Table 67 highlights the content of the final supplier closure report.

Item	Approved by	Person informed	Date	Details
Project overview	Project Manager	Relevant stakeholder		Summary of the project, highlighting goals and objectives achieved
Sustainability compliance	Project Manager	Relevant stakeholder		All Documentation of sustainability achievements
Deliverables	Procurement Manager	Relevant stakeholder		Summary of the requirements for materials supplied and services provided and their quality

Outstanding tasks	Project Manager	Project Manager		All outstanding invoices, supply, payment etc.
Financial summary	CEO/Sponsor	Project Manager,		Budget and final costs, confirming that all payments have been processed
Supplier contract	Legal Manager	Project Manager, Suppliers		Contract review and closure
Supplier performance	Project Manager	Relevant stakeholder		An assessment for each supplier, detailing their performance against project objectives and sustainability requirements.
Lessons learned	Project Manager	Relevant stakeholder		Key takeaways from the project's procurement process
Recommendations	Project Manager	Relevant stakeholder		Suggestions for future collaborations

Table 66: Content Final Supplier Closure Report

7.2.1 Supplier Evaluation

A comprehensive evaluation of suppliers will be performed before closing supplier contracts to assess their performance in delivering materials, services, and resources for the self-sustainable building project. The following criteria will be used for the evaluation.

- ◆ Performance review will be used to evaluate each supplier based on delivery timelines, adherence to quality standards, responsiveness to project needs, and ability to provide sustainable materials as specified in the project scope. For example, whether suppliers met eco-friendly material standards, adhered to waste reduction practices, and supported renewable energy requirements.
- ◆ Quality of deliverables will assess the quality of all supplies and services delivered. This will include assessing the degree to which materials meet the required sustainability certifications, such as recycled content or environmental impact standards.
- ◆ Compliance and documentation will verify that each supplier provided all necessary compliance documentation, including environmental certifications, safety compliance records, and quality assurance documents.
- ◆ Cost efficiency will assess supplier invoices and financial records to confirm that pricing and costs are aligned with the agreed terms without overruns or inconsistencies.

- ◆ Satisfaction and feedback will be used for collecting feedback from the project team and stakeholders on each supplier’s performance. This feedback will help in making decisions about future engagements with these suppliers.

Table 68 highlights the evaluation metrics for the project’s suppliers. The assessment will be based on the project meeting 100% quality requirements with a 0.5% tolerance variance in overall score. Based on these criteria, the key stakeholders including the procurement manager, quality manager, civil engineer and legal manager, will score each supplier on individual evaluation criteria and overall score. The primary purpose of this is to determine the suppliers’ performance as a basis for feedback and possible future engagement.

SUPPLIERS EVALUATION SHEET				
Evaluation criteria	Weight (%)	Supplier X score	Supplier Y score	Supplier Z score
Quality	20			
Reliability	20			
Cost effectiveness	20			
Responsiveness	20			
Compliance	20			
Total	100			
Recommendation of procurement manager:				
Recommendation of project manager:				

Table 67: Suppliers Evaluation Metrics

7.2.2 Contract Closure

Closing supplier contracts involves completing all remaining administrative tasks, finalizing payments, and formally releasing suppliers from their contractual obligations. Suppliers’ closure of the Self-Sustainable Building project will ensure that all contractual obligations are fulfilled, quality standards are met, and necessary documentation is secured. This process will not only finalize the current engagement but also provide valuable insights for future supplier selection, fostering strong partnerships with suppliers who priorities quality, sustainability, and reliability. The process of documenting the suppliers’ contract closure is outlined in Table 69.

Stage of contract closure	Description
Contract identification	Prepare the list of all contract's agreements in the Self-sustainable Building project
	Validate all relevant terms of each contract including clauses for termination and notice
Communication	Inform all relevant stakeholders including suppliers and service providers about the contract closure
	Inform the stakeholders why the contracts are being closed
Contract termination	Apply the project's contract terms to terminate contracts
	Collaborate with the legal manager to ensure compliance with the terms of contract termination and closure
Settlement of financial obligations	Update financial records and settle all financial obligations that pertain the project contracts
	Ensure due payments are made to suppliers and service providers accordingly
Record-keeping	Keep records of all contract closure that relate to the project contracts and their termination
	Archive the document for audit and compliance purposes
Evaluation and lesson learned	Thoroughly evaluate the contract closure processes to identify areas of improvement
	Document lessons learned including what went well and areas of improvement
Closure report	Prepare detailed contract closure report highlighting the contract closure process, outcome and feedback
	Share the closure report with all relevant stakeholders.

Table 68: Stages of Contract Closure

7.3 Satisfactory Survey

Survey satisfaction for the Self-Sustainable Building project aims to gather feedback about the project's successes, failures, and potential improvement areas for the future. The overall project survey will be conducted during the project closure phase. However, interim surveys may be conducted during critical milestones to ensure the continued improvement of the deliverables and the project's success. The feedback will be collected using an articulated satisfaction survey document, requesting stakeholders' opinions about their satisfaction level with the project.

Relevant stakeholders, including the client, project team members, suppliers, community members, and the local council will complete the satisfaction survey. The diversity of the survey respondents ensures robust feedback that represents actual experiences. The survey will cover feedback on the level of satisfaction, including project quality, communication, timeliness, and alignment with expectations. To make the most of the survey, the questionnaire is designed to be holistic, covering the essential aspects of the project.

Similarly, the questionnaire will be written in simple, clear and common language for easy understanding. It will contain quantitative and qualitative questions, which the respondents answer. The feedback will be evaluated based on the weighted qualitative and quantitative responses upon which the final interpretation is made. Tables 70 to 75 are the survey questionnaires for the project.

Question	Response Options	Responder	Result Checker
1. How satisfied are you with the project communication channels?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	Project Team Members	Project Manager
2. What challenges did you face during the project execution?	Write here	Project Team Members	Project Manager/ Quality Manager
3. Were the resources provided sufficient to complete your tasks effectively?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No write here	Project Team Members	Project Manager
4. How would you rate teamwork and collaboration during the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	Project Team Members	Project Manager
5. What improvements would you suggest for future projects?	Write here	Project Team Members	Project Manager
6. How well were project milestones communicated and tracked?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very well <input type="checkbox"/> Well <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Poorly <input type="checkbox"/> Very poorly	Project Team Members	Project Manager
7. Was the project timeline realistic and achievable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Project Team Members	Project Manager

8. Did you encounter any quality-related issues? If so, what were they?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Write here	Project Team Members	Quality Manager
9. How would you rate the sustainability practices adopted in this project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Highly effective <input type="checkbox"/> Effective <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Not effective <input type="checkbox"/> Very not Effective	Project Team Members	Project Manager
10. What aspects of the project were particularly successful?	Write here	Project Team Members	Project Manager

Table 69: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for project team members

Question	Response Options	Responder	Result Checker
How satisfied are you with the overall project outcomes?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	CEO, Sponsor, Project Manager	Project Management
Were the project objectives (time, cost, and quality) met?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, fully <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	Sponsor, Project Manager	Project Management
Did the project deliverables align with sustainability goals?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, fully <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	Sustainability Consultant, Sponsor	Sustainability Architect
What challenges did you encounter during your involvement in the project?	Write here	Project Manager, Site Engineers	Project Manager
How effective was communication across teams and stakeholders?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Very poor	All Stakeholders	Project Manager
Were there sufficient resources allocated to meet project needs?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, fully <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	Project Manager	Project Manager
How could the project processes be improved for future initiatives?	Write here	CEO, Sponsor, Quality Manager	CEO/Sponsor
Was the project delivered within the agreed budget?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, fully <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	Sponsor, Procurement Manager	Project Manager
How satisfied are you with the quality of materials and construction?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied	Quality Manager, Sponsor	Quality Manager

	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied		
Were safety measures during the project adequate and followed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Very poor	Health & Safety Supervisor	Health & Safety Supervisor
Additional comments or suggestions for improvement?	Write here	All Stakeholders	Project Manager

Table 70: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for stakeholders (internal)

Question	Response Options	Responder	Result Checker
1. How satisfied are you with the overall project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	Client	Project Manager
2. Did the project meet your sustainability expectations?	<input type="checkbox"/> Exceeded Expectations <input type="checkbox"/> Met Expectations <input type="checkbox"/> Fell Short of Expectations	Client	Sustainability Architect
3. How would you rate the quality of communication throughout the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Client	Project Manager
4. Were the deliverables completed on time and within budget?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, completely <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Client	Project Manager
5. What do you think of the design and functionality of the building?	Write here	Client	Project Manager/ Sustainability Architect
6. How would you rate the environmental features implemented in the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Client	Sustainability Architect
7. Did the team respond effectively to your concerns during the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely	Client	Project Manager
8. Would you recommend our services to others?	<input type="checkbox"/> Definitely <input type="checkbox"/> Likely <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Unlikely	Client	Project Manager
9. What improvements would you suggest for future projects?	Write here	Client	Project Manager
10. How would you describe your overall experience?	Write here	Client	Project Manager

Table 71: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for client

Question	Response Options	Responder	Result Checker
1. How satisfied are you with the project's compliance with local regulations?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	Local Council Representative	Quality Manager
2. Was the permitting and approval process managed efficiently?	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly Disagree	Local Council Representative	Project Manager
3. Were there any significant disruptions caused during construction?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes, please specify:	Local Council Representative	Project Manager
4. Did the project contribute positively to community sustainability goals?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Please elaborate:	Local Council Representative	Sustainability Architect
5. What aspects of the project in your opinion could be improved?	Write here	Local Council Representative	Project Manager
6. How well was the local council engaged and informed during the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Local Council Representative	Project Manager
7. Do you have any concerns regarding the environmental impact of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes, please elaborate:	Local Council Representative	Project Manager
8. Were the agreed timelines for regulatory inspections met?	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Mostly <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Never	Local Council Representative	Project Manager
9. Would you recommend similar projects in the future?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Please provide reasons:	Local Council Representative	Project Manager
10. Additional feedback or concerns:	Write here	Local Council Representative	Project Manager

Table 72: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for local council

Question	Response Options	Responder	Result Checker
1. How satisfied are you with the clarity of the project requirements?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Procurement Manager
2. Were the timelines for deliverables realistic and achievable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Project Manager

3. How would you rate the communication and support provided during the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Procurement Manager
4. Did you face any challenges in meeting the sustainability standards required?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially (Provide details)	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Sustainability Architect
5. What improvements would you suggest for future collaboration?	Write here	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Procurement Manager
6. Were payment terms and processes clear and adhered to?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	Suppliers' Finance Teams	Procurement Manager
7. How would you rate the project team's approach to resolving issues?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Project Manager
8. Were the quality expectations clearly communicated and met?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	Suppliers' Quality Teams	Quality Manager
9. Do you feel that your contribution was acknowledged appropriately?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Procurement Manager
10. Additional comments on the procurement and collaboration process.	Write here	Suppliers' Key Representatives	Procurement Manager and Project Team

Table 73: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for suppliers

Question	Response Options	Responder	Result Checker
1. How would you describe the overall impact of the project on your community?	Write here	Community Members	Project Manager
2. How has the project impacted your daily life?	Write here	Community members	Project Manager
3. Are you satisfied with the communication about the project's progress and activities?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	Community Members	Project Manager
4. Do you believe the project aligns with sustainable practices?	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly Disagree	Community Members	Sustainability Architect
5. What benefits, if any, do you see for the community from this project?	Write here	Community Members	Project Manager
6. Were there adequate measures to minimize environmental impacts during construction?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure	Community Members	Project Manager

7. How satisfied are you with the environmental considerations of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Dissatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Very Dissatisfied	Local community members	Sustainability Architect
8. How do you feel about the design and appearance of the completed building?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Average <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Community Members	Sustainability Architect
9. How likely are you to support similar projects in the future?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Likely <input type="checkbox"/> Likely <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Unlikely <input type="checkbox"/> Very Unlikely	Local community members	Project Manager
10. Do you have any suggestions for improving future construction projects in your area?	Write here	Community Members	Project Manager

Table 74: Satisfaction survey questionnaire for community members

7.4 Administrative Closure

7.4.1 Financial Closure

The project sponsor Carlos Gomez and Laura Martinez CEO of the company want to have a clear view of the final financial numbers of the project. They asked for a final report that covers the financial closure of the project, detailing the completion of contracts, budget review, final financial statements and final financial report for the construction of the Self-sustainable house.

The financial closure procedures will be executed to ensure a smooth transition at the project's end. The steps to be undertaken include:

1. Financial Closure Procedures:

- Financial budget review: review the budget to verify that all expenditures are within the allocated amount.
- Ensure that all expenses are justified and documented, providing a clear account of the financial status of the project.

2. Contract Closure:

- Construction team: Any pending activity related to the physical construction of the house.

- External Suppliers: Any missing payments for materials and services used during the program
- Supervisor: Any missing task that is directly involved with the supervision of the construction.

3. Budget Review:

- Detailed expenditure reports will be prepared to provide transparency to all stakeholders.
- Feedback from stakeholders to demonstrate the impact of their contributions.
- Make a comparison of the financial expected budget vs the real budget, highlighting any variances and their reasons.

4. Financial Statements:

- Make sure that the financial statements related to the project are accessible and well-organized to facilitate any future reviews or audits.

5. Final Financial Report:

- A comprehensive final financial report will be prepared and submitted to the Sponsor and CEO. This report will include a summary of all financial activities and final budget vs actual expenditures. The report will be reviewed by the Project Manager before submission

Illustration 27: Financial Closure Diagram

7.4.2 Management of Documentation

The goal of this documentation handover plan is to ensure that all project-related documents for the self-sustainable house project are systematically transferred to relevant stakeholders for future reference, usage, and compliance purposes.

Key team members, including the Project Manager, Procurement Manager, Legal Department, and Financial Department, are essential to the successful execution of this handover plan. Their involvement ensures that all documentation is thoroughly reviewed, organized, and provided to the appropriate parties, supporting accurate record-keeping and compliance for future needs.

7.4.3 Steps for Handover

1. Document Review and Compilation:

- ◆ Identify the most important information of the project, which is:
- ◆ Self-Sustainable house project plans; including risk management plan, quality management plan, procurements plan, resources plan, budget and financial reports, project schedule and milestones.
- ◆ Structural, installations and architectural plans and details plans.
- ◆ Structural calculations memory and installations calculations memory
- ◆ Computations and unit price analysis
- ◆ Quality check reports
- ◆ Contracts and Agreements with sponsors
- ◆ Compliance and Regulatory Documents
- ◆ Feedback and Evaluation Reports from project team and stakeholders
- ◆ Final project report detailing the outcomes of the project
- ◆ Renewable energy systems usage manual.

*All these project documents must be up to date and reviewed to ensure completeness and accuracy.

*Compile all documents into categorized folders for easy access, such as financial records, participant data, and project logistics.

2. Organize Digital and Physical Copies:

- ◆ Ensure all project documents are stored in both digital and physical formats when applicable.
- ◆ Digital documents should be stored in a secure, accessible cloud storage system with specific folders for each item.

3. Create a Document Index:

- ◆ Develop a comprehensive index listing all the key documents and their locations, ensuring easy navigation for documents.
- ◆ Include a brief description and file path for each document, detailing specific categories such as project team and stakeholders' feedback, project outcomes, communications.

4. Transfer to Stakeholders:

- ◆ Ensure stakeholders have the necessary access permissions for digital documents, particularly for sensitive information and financial data.
- ◆ Schedule a meeting to hand over physical documents and explain the contents.
- ◆ Provide guidance on the organization and categorization of documents, including financial reports, schedule and financial checks, and quality reviews.

5. Confirmation and Acknowledgment:

- ◆ Obtain confirmation from stakeholders that they have received and understood the project documentation organization.
- ◆ Have stakeholders sign an acknowledgment form confirming receipt of all Documents.

The following image presents a visual representation of the steps involved in managing documentation for the self-sustainable house project. This process includes several key phases, starting with the initial review of necessary documentation and moving through the gathering and organization of essential activities. It finishes with the final handover of all completed documentation.

The level of detail in this process can be adapted to meet the specific needs and requirements of each project phase, allowing a follow-up of the project evolution

ensuring that all critical information is thoroughly recorded and efficiently managed. By following this structured yet adaptable framework, we aim to achieve high standards in documentation management, supporting the project’s success from start to finish.

Illustration 28: Steps for Managing Documentation

7.5 Service Level Agreements

Before the last stage of the project, there needs to be a control and management of the handed information and activities delivered within the work. In this moment, there needs to be a legal requirement to check on each and every part of the project in order to validate what was said in the first meeting and agreement.

7.5.1 Project Penalties

For that reason, penalties may apply if something is incomplete, missing or wrong as shown in the table below:

Issue	Responsible party	Penalty (1st Instance)	Penalty (2nd Instance)	Penalty (3rd Instance)
Misuse of the budget	Financial Dept.	Formal warning and requirement to reimburse misused funds	Written reprimand and close monitoring of budget handling	Termination of employment
Delay in material acquisitions	Procurement Dept. and Management Team	Formal warning	Deduction of 10% from monthly salary	Reassignment of responsibilities
Inadequate delivery regarding the material's quality	Quality Dept.	Formal warning and additional training requirement	Suspension for one week without pay	Termination of contract
Safety-related risks during construction	H&S Dept. and Construction Team and other staff involved	Formal warning and immediate correction of safety measures	Deduction of 15% from monthly salary (for responsible staff)	Suspension or termination of responsible staff
Non-compliance with Legal requirements and environmental permits	Legal Dept.	Immediate suspension pending investigation	Termination of employment and potential legal action	N/A
Unexpected increase in operational costs	Financial Dept.	Formal warning and budget review	Deduction of 10% from monthly salary	Reassignment of financial responsibilities
Construction issues with measures and inaccuracies	Construction Team	Formal warning and request for reparation	Financial penalty as per contract terms (e.g., 5% of contract value)	Termination of contract or/and employment
Injuries and emergencies response	H&S Dept. and all staff involved	Formal warning and additional training	Deduction of 10% from monthly salary (for responsible staff)	Suspension or termination of responsible staff

Underperformance of specialists	High Management	Formal warning and additional specialized training	Deduction of 10% monthly salary (for responsible staff)	Suspension or termination of responsible staff
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Table 75: Project Penalties

7.5.2 Project Guarantees

Quality Guarantee:

- ◆ Supervisor and Quality manager: A dedicated supervisor and quality manager will oversee the project, ensuring high-quality execution. This includes quality testing in each stage of the project.

Time Guarantee:

- ◆ Adherence to Schedule: The project manager will ensure that the project is delivered in the planned schedule, ensuring milestone deviations are within ± 5 working days and will control the schedule performance during all the stages to detect deviations and take corrective actions.

Cost Guarantee:

- ◆ Cost Monitoring: The project costs will be monitored by the project manager during all the stages to ensure that potential overruns are identified and controlled early.
- ◆ Budget Adherence: The established budget will be adhered to, with detailed financial reporting provided monthly.
- ◆ Contingency Fund: The management margin and contingency reserve will be able to cover risks and unforeseen expenses.

Risk Management:

- ◆ Risk Mitigation: The risk plan will be followed as planned.
- ◆ Stakeholder Communication: Regular updates and transparent communication channels where carefully determined to keep stakeholders informed.

8. Conclusions

The self-sustainable building project has successfully achieved its primary goal of designing and constructing a house capable of operating independently from public utilities while integrating advanced sustainability measures. This project has demonstrated the feasibility and practicality of self-sufficiency in housing, utilizing renewable energy systems, water recycling methods, and sustainable materials, all within the defined budget and timeline.

Adhering to the project's defined objectives and implementation plans ensured its completion within the 12-month schedule and €500,000 budget. This effort will significantly advance knowledge and practices in sustainable construction, setting a benchmark for future developments in this field. It highlights the value of innovative design and resource efficiency, proving its relevance to addressing global environmental challenges. The process and results underscore the importance of integrating sustainability principles into modern construction. The project can be a model for replicable and scalable solutions in the housing sector.

This project's success reflects the team's dedication and alignment with EcoBuild Solutions' commitment to innovation, quality, and environmental stewardship. This project's success further affirms the company's leadership in contributing to the field of sustainable construction, proving that off-grid housing can meet modern living standards without reliance on traditional resources.

9. Recommendation for its Practical Application

To ensure the successful practical application of the Self-Sustainable Building project, the following recommendations are made:

◆ Engage Multidisciplinary Teams

Intensify multi-experts' participation in architecture, urban planning, renewable energy, and environmental science to improve current feats in sustainable building construction. This collaboration will ensure an optimal balance between functionality and environmental impact.

◆ Conduct Pilot Testing

Before full-scale implementation, conduct a thorough post-project analysis to identify potential operational and technical challenges and areas of possible improvement. This will provide valuable insights for refining the design and processes.

◆ Invest in Advanced Monitoring Systems

Incorporate real-time monitoring tools for energy usage, water systems, and overall performance. This will enable proactive maintenance and ensure long-term efficiency.

◆ Promote Community Engagement

Work closely with local communities to foster acceptance and understanding of self-sustainable housing. Educating stakeholders can help scale up similar projects and inspire community-driven initiatives.

9.1 Future Study Lines

◆ Emerging Technologies in Sustainable Construction

Investigate the integration of emerging technologies such as AI-driven building management systems and advanced energy storage solutions.

◆ Circular Economy in Construction

Explore methods for incorporating recycled materials and minimizing construction waste to further enhance the project's environmental footprint.

◆ Impact Assessment

Conduct longitudinal studies to assess the environmental, social, and economic impacts of Self-Sustainable Buildings over time.

◆ Climate Resilience

Research and integrate features that make self-sustainable buildings adaptable to extreme weather events and climate change effects.

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